

Innovative and Inclusive Democratic Spaces for Deliberation and Participation

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D4.3 Guideline for participatory processes

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Summary	
<p>This deliverable sums up the results of a transdisciplinary co-production process leading to the production of these guidelines on how to make participatory processes easier to access. It expands on the methodology, provides general advice based on evidence, informs on the status quo of design-choices for each pilot and it recommends tools and methods and provides further advice to enhance inclusivity. Concluding remarks touch upon further challenges to be managed, such as the interrelation between design-choices, data protection and security, documentation, possible aims of (UX) testing, and the usage of digital platforms.</p>	
Plain Language Summary	
<p>This document explains how we created guidelines on how to make participatory processes easy to access.</p> <p>It explains the methods used.</p> <p>It gives advice based on general evidence.</p> <p>It explains the choices made in each pilot project.</p>	

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It compares these choices among them where relevant.

It recommends tools and methods to improve inclusivity.

The conclusion of this document explains the challenges that we will face:

- how are design choices connected?
- what are the issues with data protection and security?
- what are the documentation needs?
- what are the goals of user experience (UX) tests?
- what are the goals of the use of digital platforms?

Author List		
Organization	Name	Contact Information
NEXUS	Volkan Sayman	sayman@nexusinstitut.de
NEXUS	Thomas Blanchet	blanchet@nexusinstitut.de
NEXUS	Maria Serrato	maria.serratonexus.de
NEXUS	Ansgar Düben	dueben@nexusinstitut.de

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	21/12/24	Submitted	Sandra Szasz - UPF

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Acronyms	
CIB	Cibervoluntarios
DoA	Description of the Action
iAP2	International Association for Public Participation
iDEM	Innovative and Inclusive Democratic Spaces for Deliberation and Participation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
MAC	The National MicroElectronics Centre
NEXUS	Nexus Institute for Cooperation management and interdisciplinary research
UOL	University of Leeds
UX/UCD	User-centred design

1. Introduction

This deliverable sketches out the typical steps of a participatory process. It provides general advice on designing participatory processes and detailed recommendations to enhance their inclusivity. These guidelines also shed light on the evolution and status quo of the still ongoing discussions on each pilot's main design-decisions. The deliverable is the outcome of and reflects transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge (in a similar way e.g. Schneider et al 2019), involving successive steps of grasping uncertainties, co-producing new knowledge and creating a shared understanding of the nature of participatory processes and challenges of inclusivity in general, and the pilots' designs in particular.

The co-productive activities leading to D4.3. were accompanied and informed by the collaborative research activities in T1.2¹, T4.1² and T4.2³ as the iDEM project's members were involved in all of these tasks at the same time for a period of several months (July 2024-November 2024). In particular, the results presented in D4.1. *Report on the Engagements of Hard-to-reach-groups and vulnerable populations* have been considered. Worth noting that D4.1. is a report which sums the analysis of more than 20 interviews with experts in the fields of inclusion, disabilities and participation and an extensive literature review. Relevant results were added where they contribute to clarity and guidance in better including vulnerable groups in the pilots of the iDEM project.

We stick to and expand on the distinctions already made in the context of the project. We distinguish three phases of a participatory process: *before*, *during* and *after* deliberation to reflect the temporal structure. As a matter of enabling temporal synchronization of the participatory process' results with other social realities and practices, we introduce the policy- or decision-making cycle with its five stages (OECD 2022). This will allow the pilot's project teams to better link the results of the participatory process to policy-making. Organizers will be able to reflect with adequate precision on the question *which kind of input the participatory process is supposed to produce for which kind and step of the policy-making process*.

Finally, we employ the distinction of formats, methods and tools with reference to Schweizer et al. (2022: 34). The terms "formats," "methods," and "tools" distinguish levels and practices of participatory processes. "Formats" refer to structured frameworks that organise citizens or stakeholders in decision-making processes through a series of steps, from preparation to follow-up. These formats are implemented using various "methods" (e.g., group discussions, voting), which allow participants to engage and contribute within structured and proven practices. However, as methods alone are insufficient to facilitate full participation, the usage of tools is most often a substantial mediator to realize formats in face-to-face and digital

¹ T1.2 Identify accessibility barriers to democratic participation for people with cognitive disabilities and their marginalisation of democratic spaces.

² T4.1 Comprehensive assessment of the engagements of hard to reach groups and vulnerable populations in participatory and deliberative processes

³ T4.2 Enhancing the production of inclusiveness by facilitators (analysis/research).

interaction. Therefore, we define "tools" as the specific resources or instruments (like software or physical materials) that support methods and formats, either online or offline.

These guidelines refer to three guidelines as main sources. One is the OECD's guideline on participatory processes from 2022 (OECD 2022), which is one of the most encompassing guidelines making reference to several previous guideline publications of the OECD itself, to guidelines of practitioner organizations and think-tanks (*Involve* from the UK and *MassLBP* from Canada; *The Governance Lab* from the USA) and to various researchers' contributions.

A second guideline used as a central resource here is a practitioner's guide for inclusive deliberative and participative processes issued by the Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue (2020), Vancouver (Canada). The fact that Canada is a multilingual and multi ethnic society materializes in these guidelines. Participation is directed towards specific communities and their leaders, such as those who "... have faced historic and ongoing marginalization due to their race, ethnicity, religion, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, socioeconomic background, citizenship status, or other identities and lived experiences. These groups are often under-represented in leadership and engagement processes due to overt exclusion and/or systemic physical, social and financial barriers." (Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 5). To ensure that the guidelines are of high practical value, the guide was co-produced "... through a participatory research and consultation process led by Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue from May 2019 - January 2020, including seven focus groups with community members and representatives from government and civil society, a review of over 40 related resources and interviews with 13 public engagement practitioners." (Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 1). The third guideline we are referring to (Tomloyova 2024) here was issued by GlobSEC, committed to enhancing security, prosperity and sustainability in Europe and throughout the world."⁴

1.1. Objective of the task

The Innovative and Inclusive Democratic Spaces for Deliberation and Participation (iDEM) project aims to develop solutions to remove language barriers that hinder the participation of individuals with communication difficulties who are marginalized in democratic processes due to the inherent complexity of the language used in documents, debates, and discourses.

The project is exploring the limitations of the current marginalization in deliberative processes, particularly regarding people with communication access needs. In the project we address people having special communication needs from three social groups, people with intellectual disabilities, migrants, and senior citizens. We will use a user-centered design (UCD/UX) approach to develop a technological solution that contributes to creating more accessible and inclusive democratic spaces by simplifying texts. Thus, the iDEM project implements natural language

⁴ <https://www.globsec.org/who-we-are/about-us> (retrieved at 25.11.24)

processing (NLP) technologies to facilitate reading, comprehension, and simplification of information, to promote equitable democratic participation.

The main objective of the task T4.3⁵ is to - based on the results of T4.1 - make a first selection of the various formats and tools that will be implemented in the three pilots (T4.5⁶). NEXUS carried out an internal survey in order to assess the specific needs and requirements identified in T4.1 In a second step, NEXUS will organize participatory design workshops to collectively create a tangible outcome that can serve as a pre-prototype for the pilot implementation.

Relevant contents of these guidelines were developed in a series of two consecutive workshops, monthly meetings within the scope of WP4⁷ and a thorough review of the drafted methodology of each pilot after both workshops. These guidelines shall provide an orientation to the readers interested in enhancing the inclusiveness of participatory processes and especially to those, who are in charge of designing and implementing pilot case studies in the iDEM project. In order to contextualize the range of potential design choices, we refer to evidence and experience from existing guidelines for citizen participation processes (OECD 2022). Further, the following guidelines sum up the status quo of the discussions on the main design areas of each pilot. They thereby contribute to a reflexive design process and enhance the epistemic comparability of the main features of all pilots.

1.2. Link with the other WPS and tasks

Within WP1⁸, this deliverable is related to *T1.2 Report on barriers, strategies, and support to increase inclusion*, as T1.2 investigates the accessibility barriers faced by individuals with communication difficulties, including those with intellectual disabilities, in participatory and democratic processes. T4.3 is equally related to T1.2, T1.4 and to T4.1. While T1.2 mainly focuses on the barriers and problems, T4.1 analyzes the solutions to overcome those barriers, in forms of techniques, methods and formats enhancing inclusivity and accessibility in participatory processes. Both tasks and respective deliverables D1.2⁹ and D4.1¹⁰ will provide valuable information and input within this deliverable. It is important here to differentiate the results of D1.4 "Piloting methodology roadmap" from D.4.3. The D.1.4 details a range of relevant thoughts on the structure of pilots, it sketches out a theoretical framework for UX-testing and it identifies opportunities for testing the iDEM service and as well as the objectives of testing (utility of the product, usability, credibility, desirability, accessibility and a valuable experience). Unlike D1.4, D4.3 focuses on the design of pilots from the perspective of deliberative democracy and

⁵ T4.3 Solution Ideation

⁶ T4.5 Pilots implementation

⁷ WP4 User Engagement, Piloting, & Monitoring Deliberative & Participatory Democracy

⁸ WP1 Theoretical Foundations: Power Structures, Inequalities, Intersectionality in Deliberative & Participatory Democratic Spaces

⁹ D1.2 Report on barriers, strategies, and support to increase inclusion

¹⁰ D4.1 Report on engagements of hard to reach groups and vulnerable populations in participatory and deliberative processes

provides more details on central trade-offs regarding design choices and their possible impact on the overall quality of the deliberative process and testing alike.

Within WP4, the task is related to *T.4.2. Enhancing the production of inclusiveness by facilitators*, where the focus will be on inclusive facilitation and moderation techniques and *T 4.1. Assessment of the engagements of hard to reach groups and vulnerable populations*.

T.4.3. Solution ideation and the respective D4.3. will especially rely on the insights from D4.1. in order to build and implement the methodology for piloting the case studies.

2. Methodology

The methodology orienting the work streams leading to these guidelines is that of transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge and competence building (Schneider et al 2019). The project's members' discussions and related research activities about how to best design each pilot were organized and structured by the Nexus team over a period of around four months, starting in August 2024. During two workshops (one in-person and one online) and monthly WP4 sessions, the different experts within the consortium engaged in a transdisciplinary debate on how to best design three pilots, with each stage of the debate leading to a successively sharpened version of a pre-prototype. A survey conducted shortly before the second workshop in October 2024 provided data from each partner in the consortium about their views on which paths should be taken regarding key design features of all pilots. The second workshop, a set of transdisciplinary interactions, led to the fixation of first decisions on the pilot's design. These were discussed and reviewed afterwards by those partners in charge of implementing the pilots.

Relevant discussions and research activities were structured by a temporal scheme (before, during and after deliberation), a specific focus on vulnerable groups' barriers in participative processes and formats, methods and tools to overcome those barriers, and finally, criteria indicating a high quality of participative processes (Tomlyova 2024; OECD 2022). Finally, considerations about the question in which ways interesting variations between the pilots (which are then open to exploration by researchers from the consortium) can be produced while keeping ethical standards high and enabling a structured implementation of each pilot in line with its Description of the Action (DoA) played a role.

Overview on relevant research steps activities contributing to this deliverable

Date	Kind of activity	Description of activity
01/29-01/30/2024	Kick-off meeting in Barcelona, Spain	Presentation of the scope of WP4 by NEXUS and discussion of next steps by all

		partners
10/07/2024	Online feedback workshop on the prototype	Session to assess the results of a first user test with project members als examinees, script was circulated beforehand and was supposed to be followed to guide the user testing
08/2024-11/2024	Research and analysis for Deliverables 1.2. and 4.1.	Design, preparation and implementation of focus groups in Barcelona, Madrid and Bologna by all partners; more than 20 expert and stakeholder interviews; collaborative literature analysis by all partners; thematic coding, problem-oriented analysis and documentation of results and recommendations by NEXUS
08/10-11/2024	Monthly WP4 meetings	Regular exchange on work progress concerning task 4.3. by all partners
01/10-15/10/2024	Drafting & implementation of an internal survey and analysis of the results	Analysis of potential needs of respondents and requirements of inclusive participatory processes by NEXUS
16/10-17/10/2024	Participatory design workshop in Barcelona	Input on deliberative and participative processes and presentation of the survey's results by NEXUS; discussion of the results and co-productive group works by all partners
17/10/2024-25/11/2024	Review, discussion and refinement of the workshop's results	Review of the documented results by all partners, coordinated by NEXUS

Table 1 Methodological Steps (Own Elaboration)

2.1. Implementation of a survey

The survey was set up and circulated among the project's members shortly before the 2nd workshop in Barcelona was held (16/10-17/10/2024). In general, in the survey's design, a specific focus was placed on the phase before deliberation, as in October 2024 all pilots would still be in their preparatory phase, with almost no design activities having taken place before that date.

Further, decisions made during the preparatory phase will have a lasting impact on the (possible) range of design choices (path-dependency) and possibilities to adapt to new circumstances later on.

For example, if in a pilot it was decided not to conduct a training with the app or accessibility assessments with future participants from the outset, this would be consequential both for the participants themselves and the quality of the overall participatory process. Participants may be overwhelmed by adapting to a series of unknown circumstances such as the process itself, unknown people and in addition, an unknown assistive tool. The quality of the process may be distorted by too much attention and time being consumed by learning to use a tool supposed to be a supplementary tool enhancing the inclusion into the actual process. On the contrary, deciding not to train participants in using the app from the outset can also create an epistemologically interesting variation between the three pilots, in case the other two pilots provide such a training. The examples should have demonstrated the importance of discussing these questions as early as possible for each of the pilots and also the productivity of discussing these questions with all partners from the outset.

The survey was structured in three parts: questions concerning the phase before (14 questions), during (5 questions) and after (2 questions) the main participative process. The questionnaire is to be found in Annex 1.

2.2. Organization of workshops

2.2.1. Workshop 1 (Online)

The workshop took place on the 10th of July and was organized by NEXUS with the help of MAC, the company in the consortium responsible for the software's design and implementation. It was preceded by the release of V0.1 of the app, its circulation in the consortium and its evaluation by MAC through an evaluation questionnaire. The evaluation questionnaire contained questions on the digital hardware and the digital participation platforms the respondent regularly uses. It then required the respondent to do 7 tasks¹¹ with the iDEM App described in more detail in a Google Form and record any problems they encountered. Two further questionnaires on Usability and General Feedback followed.

The results of this first internal evaluation among project partners was then presented on an online workshop on the 10th of July. The results were discussed and first implications for the pilots were put forward. The discussion was led by three central questions, which could not be answered to a full extent but this was not necessary at that point. The three questions were:

¹¹ The tasks were: 1. Run the iDEM App on your Android or Apple mobile phone, 2. Set your User Preferences, 3. Input your text, 4. Make your text more understandable, 5. Output Texts, 6. Participate in an iDEM pilot democratic space - Barcelona, 7. Participate in an external democratic space - Clare.

Does the current status of the design of the app's interface satisfy the requirements of deployment in typical situations of participatory processes? Is it usable for people with cognitive disabilities or elderly people? How does MAC intend to organize the further development of the app? Conducting these discussions at such an early stage proved to be fruitful since it provided an opportunity to readjust expectations towards the app's functionalities and to imagine potential developments.

2.2.2. Workshop 2 (Barcelona)

The second workshop was organized by NEXUS and took place in Barcelona on the 16th and 17th of October 2024. The methodology of the workshop mirrored a commitment to reduce the complexity resulting from the amount of (interrelated) design-decisions to take under conditions of uncertainty. It therefore asked all partners in the consortium to take part in a series of group activities, including the more technical partners, which could be realized to a certain degree. It was preceded by the circulation of a questionnaire which was responded to by 14 project members. The results were analyzed before the workshop and presented in Barcelona. The technical partners took part in one out of three group activities and the general discussion. This contributed substantially to creating a shared understanding of common goals and challenges concerning the piloting, the expected outcomes of the participatory processes and the opportunities for, and aims of testing the app.

The workshop was organized in five blocks stretching over one and a half days. The first block contextualized the workshop, explained the method and provided an input differentiating participation from deliberation. The second part centred around the needs and requirements of the organizers for preparing the phase before deliberation. Similarly, the third and fourth part repeated the structure of the second part for the phases during and after deliberation. The fifth part was supposed to sum up and synthesize the partial plans and create a bigger picture for each pilot and compare them with each other. Parts two, three and five comprised three consecutive exercises: an individual re-reading of the survey's results, a brainwriting session and the drawing of a roadmap in small groups. Each of the three phases was completed by a presentation and discussion of the results in the bigger group. Discussions in part five on the second day of the workshop were documented by NEXUS in the form of a table. This table was circulated among the project's members and the organizers of the pilots in particular for further comments and refinement. The results of this reviewed table fed into this deliverable. Similarly, Milestone 3¹², the case study methodology was informed by the second workshop's results.

3. Results of the survey

Commitment to Collaborative Pilots

¹² Milestone 3 was attained in November 2024. It contains a structured description of the case study's methodology.

Participants expressed a strong commitment to the collaborative implementation of pilots, covering roles from design to execution, software integration, and evaluation. The number of respondents is 14.

Figure 1- Response chart to pilot implementation

Relevant Topics

Respondents highlighted the importance of addressing local issues, such as urban mobility, transportation, municipal security, and welfare services, alongside broader challenges like climate change, misinformation, and digital inclusion.

Main relevant topics identified to be discussed in planned participatory process

Figure 2 - Overview on the most recurring topics

Event Duration, Structure, and Participant Representation

Participatory events will generally consist of 2 to 5 sessions, each lasting 3 to 4 hours, divided into phases like preparation, information-sharing, deliberation, and feedback. Some prefer shorter, recurring meetings to build trust, while others favor standalone events with app-based tools. Sessions are planned for 10-60 participants, with an emphasis on diverse representation,

including migrants, older adults, and those with intellectual disabilities. Larger groups may be divided into specialized subgroups to meet varying needs.

Figure 3 - Illustration of the responses for the event duration and frequency

Group Dynamics and Composition

Small group discussions, typically with 3 to 8 participants (preferably 4-5), will foster focused, inclusive interactions. Respondents emphasized balancing group demographics to ensure diverse representation across gender, age, ethnicity, migration status, and disabilities. Some respondents advocated for quotas to ensure vulnerable groups, such as migrants, elderly individuals, and people with disabilities, are adequately represented. Other considerations included avoiding group dynamics that could hinder participation, particularly for individuals with intellectual disabilities.

Recruitment Strategies and Accessibility

Recruitment will largely rely on partnerships with NGOs and local organizations, with additional efforts to ensure broad representation through sortition or open calls. Respondents stressed the importance of gathering socio-demographic data, including gender, age, and disability status, to tailor participatory processes to target groups and to conduct an informed selection. Invitations will be sent using accessible communication methods such as WhatsApp, email, phone calls, and written materials in easy-to-read formats, ensuring no barriers to participation.

Agenda-Setting and Support Needs

Most respondents favor involving stakeholders like facilitators¹³, representatives of target groups, and experts in setting the agenda. While some advocate for excluding political figures, there is broad consensus that agendas should align with participants' interests and past research. Support needs include ethical guidance, help in creating accessible materials, and collaboration with local administrations to define relevant topics.

Co-Design with Participants

The value of involving participants in the design phase was debated. While some favor co-designing schedules or gathering input during preparatory meetings, others expressed concerns about confusing participants. Feedback collection through initial meetings was commonly proposed. Support needs for co-design include guidance on co-production methodologies and resources for organizing preparatory meetings.

¹³ We distinguish moderators from facilitators. Moderators are professionally skilled individuals being trained in moderation, conflict resolution and the handling of deadlocked communicative situations. Facilitators are people who support individuals with intellectual disabilities.

Preferred Formats and Support Needs

Respondents favored participatory formats like mini-publics (e.g. citizen assemblies), and small-group discussions, with methods such as Open Space Technology (OST) and "living library" approaches being considered. Support needs for format development include web platforms with accessible documentation and examples of participatory methods to adapt for target groups.

Facilitators and Ethical Considerations

The importance of facilitators to ensure meaningful contributions, especially for participants with disabilities, was highlighted. Ethical considerations focused on respecting privacy, ensuring voluntary participation, and balancing representation. Protective measures for vulnerable groups, such as anonymity and safeguarding against power imbalances, were also emphasized. Additionally, some respondents suggested compensating participants through vouchers or certificates of attendance, while others cited policy restrictions against financial incentives.

Small Group Discussions

Small group discussions, particularly with around 5 participants per group, were considered essential for fostering engagement, especially for participants facing language barriers or cognitive challenges. Moderators and tailored activities will support these sessions, ensuring diversity and addressing power imbalances. Discussions will last between 20 minutes and two hours, with flexibility to adjust based on participant engagement. Breaks and feedback are encouraged to optimize session flow.

Moderation and Moderator Training

Moderators will be trained on group facilitation techniques, communication strategies for participants with intellectual disabilities, and simplifying complex language. Some respondents proposed internal moderators familiar with target groups, while others emphasized the need for external, professional facilitators. Support for moderator training, including guidelines and templates, was identified as crucial for addressing the unique challenges of the target audience.

Expert Involvement and Digital Tools

Experts will be involved in discussions, presenting information through accessible formats like slides and brochures. Training for experts in easy communication and visual aids was highlighted as a key need. Digital tools, including projectors, tablets, and apps like iDEM, will support information sharing and engagement. Respondents emphasized the need for user-friendly tools, with clear instructions provided to ensure effective usage.

iDEM Integration and Digital Participation Platforms

The iDEM app will play a central role throughout the participatory process—before events for information access, during sessions for content simplification, and after for feedback and follow-up. Participants and facilitators will need training to use the app effectively. Digital participation platforms like Decidim will also be used to collect feedback and engage participants

before and after events. Some respondents suggested testing the iDEM app in various contexts to evaluate its adaptability.

Expected Inputs to policy- and decision-making

The expected outcomes include recommendations, reports, voting results, and participant-generated ideas. These will be communicated through accessible formats such as videos with subtitles, easy-to-read documents, and visual aids. Some respondents proposed participant-led video recordings to enhance engagement and authenticity. The expectation is that the outcomes will be considered by local and regional political institutions, though there is uncertainty about adoption.

Training and Knowledge Resources

Training priorities include techniques for moderation, managing group dynamics, and creating accessible materials for participants with intellectual disabilities or language barriers. Knowledge resources, such as best practices, past experiences, and examples of successful participatory processes, were identified as essential. Additionally, exchanges with experts and associations are considered crucial for enhancing the design and implementation of participatory processes.

Additional Feedback

Several respondents highlighted the importance of learning from European-level participatory events, particularly regarding multilingualism and fostering transparency across diverse participant groups to improve democratic processes.

4. Guidelines for participatory processes

Section four is structured by the temporality of participatory processes, seen from the perspective of the organizers. It therefore reflects an order of decisions to make and points to reflect on for those who will organize a participatory process. Each of the three phases is divided by subheadings focusing on a stage of the process. Each of the subheadings is divided into a section with general advice, a section describing the evolution of the discussions in the consortium, a table with the status quo of design choices of each pilot¹⁴ and, if available, tools, methods and recommendations concerning that point taken from D4.1.

The order of the subheadings reflects our recommendations regarding the question which steps should be followed first, second, third and so on. Yet, determining the expected outcome of the inputs of the participation process, defining the target group and an adequate recruitment method and deciding on an issue are interrelated decisions. The fourth key decision interrelated with the aforementioned ones is the decision on the format. All these decisions will be arrived at in a complex process in which path dependencies, local policy-making and participation practices

¹⁴ The contents of the tables summing up the status quo of design choices are the outcome of a table which was used to document the second day of the workshop in Barcelona in October 2024. The table was reviewed and refined by the partners after that workshop and its most recent results are displayed here.

and cultures (Schritt/Voß 2023) and the availability of resources will interact. That is to say, that these guidelines do not intend to prescribe step by step how the organizers of the pilots shall proceed to implement *the* process. Rather, it describes the necessary steps to take when organizing a participatory process in more detail, and it sheds light on conditions under which decisions by the organizers are made and on basic interdependencies between design choices.¹⁵

4.1. Before the main process

4.1.1. Involving participants from the outset into the design to enhance inclusivity and accessibility:

General Advice:

Different guidelines in the field of participatory and deliberative democracy stress that especially when involving vulnerable groups into a participatory process, it is of high importance to involve participants before the actual process starts, to make participants familiar with the process' design, digital tools and the issue at stake, and to include participants in relevant design decisions from the outset (OECD 2022: 21).

Concretely, the guidelines of the Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue (2020: 22) recommends "... work in partnership with the community throughout the planning process.". The authors further state that working with marginalized communities shall be based on trust, respect, collaborative and reciprocal relationships. Concretely, they suggest sharing power and decision-making competences with their target communities: to dedicate time for building personal relationships, to partner with community organizers and leaders and finally, to co-create the engagement itself (e.g. designing engagement approaches) (Simon Fraser University's Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 42). Similarly, the OECD guide to public participation recommends to implement opportunities for team-building before the actual deliberation process. Concretely, this means that "... members of the process meet one another and establish the values that will guide their deliberation. During some cases they also receive training on understanding biases and critical thinking. This phase creates the conditions for their deliberation to be possible in the latter stages." (OECD 2022: 83).

Broadly speaking, training during preparatory sessions can focus on two aspects. First, the training can focus on teaching participants the specificity of the process itself and to improve the way participants may navigate the process and thereby, to reduce the risk of confusion or alienation. An example of good practice in this regard is the training provided by the members of the project team of DEMOTEC¹⁶, a European project experimenting with Participatory Budgeting in seven European countries (Cyprus, Greece, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, Romania, and

¹⁵ The interdependencies between design-choices meant here are those between the choice for the topic, the format, the recruitment method and the expected outcome(-s).

¹⁶ <https://demotec-project.eu/overview/> (retrieved at the 27th of November 2024)

Scotland) (OECD 2022: 82). They provided video tutorials¹⁷ to help future participants understand the structure of the process and the ways they can navigate it.

A second focus of pretraining can be to provide the skills necessary to make use of assistive (digital) tools within the process and to explain the opportunities and limits of those tools. This second focus is especially important given the “digital divide”, that is the uneven distribution of digital tools and skills within society (OECD 2022: 51). “It is important to avoid the emergence of new forms of “digital exclusion” (i.e., not being able to take advantage of digital services and opportunities). For example, men, urban residents, and young people are more likely to be online than women, rural populations, and older persons (International Telecommunication Union, 2021[22]). When possible, digital tools should be implemented alongside in-person methods, to increase inclusion and bridge the digital divide.” (OECD 2022: 51). In this respect, a pre-training with a focus on how the digital tools are supposed to be used in the participative process can enhance both the digital competencies of future participants and may help organizers to get an overview on the distribution of digital skills among the group of their participants. Thus, the risk of overwhelming (some) participants with digital tools can be reduced and the organizers may adapt their strategy to use digital tools in their respective processes.

In the case of iDEM the issue of pre-training is particularly important because all pilots target a specific mix of different vulnerable groups (people with intellectual disabilities, elderly people and migrants) and the pilots are supposed to make use of the iDEM tool at some (still to be defined) occasions within the process.

Evolvement of discussions throughout the design stage:

At the time the survey was conducted, partners in the participatory design Workshop in Barcelona recognized the need for effective preparatory sessions to ensure participants understood both the participatory process and the iDEM functionalities. Following the discussions after the Barcelona workshop, the importance of structured pre-training was reinforced, leading to a consensus on implementing comprehensive preparatory sessions tailored to participant needs. Before the survey, training needs were recognized but not uniformly addressed across pilots. The participatory design Workshop in Barcelona facilitated a shared understanding of the critical role of comprehensive training in utilizing the iDEM app effectively.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Pre-training focuses on participants' understanding of both the participatory process and iDEM functionalities. This preparation stage helps familiarize participants with the tools and the aims of the deliberation. Participants and facilitators receive specific training in using the iDEM service, especially
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¹⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j8BClck-9Mk&list=PLVxj_b_jwQNcws94O4FXCNRiqqdhtNc-A (retrieved at 27th of November 2024)

	during the preparation and discussion phases. Training focuses on text simplification and sharing information through the app.
Madrid	A similar pre-training phase is applied, ensuring participants are well-versed in the event's goals. Training is delivered in multiple sessions lasting three hours each, with a focus on maximizing engagement during the main process. The need for training is identified, but there is uncertainty about whether short guides or videos are required. A cognitive accessibility assessment will be conducted to ensure that participants can use the app effectively.
Barcelona	There will be a pre-training phase where they will share the app with the participant association, and the sessions will be divided into four events, each lasting two hours, which might involve some form of introductory activities. Training is provided for both facilitators and participants in using the iDEM app. Expectations for using the app are clearly communicated, and facilitators ensure that participants are comfortable with the technology. It is important to remember that to ensure that training sessions are beneficial for everyone, there should be videos with tutorials in plain language explaining how the app works and the possibilities it offers.
Comparison	All pilots will have pre-training to show the app and how it works to participants. All pilots include training for both participants and facilitators in using the iDEM app. This ensures that everyone involved can effectively engage with the technology.

Evolvement of discussions throughout the design stage:

To improve participatory processes and ensure inclusivity, several tools and recommendations can be implemented. These measures focus on empowering participants, addressing individual needs, and involving vulnerable groups in the design and decision-making stages.

Tools and Methods for Inclusivity

Establishing **advisory teams with target group representation** is a key strategy to make participatory processes more inclusive. These teams, composed of members from vulnerable groups, play a crucial role in shaping the process design, selecting relevant questions, and identifying appropriate experts. Their involvement ensures that the process is informed by the lived experiences and perspectives of those it aims to include.

A **preliminary empowerment phase** is another important tool for building confidence and understanding among participants. By offering early empowerment sessions that include rights-based training and awareness activities, organizers can equip participants with the knowledge and self-assurance they need to engage meaningfully in the process.

To address individual needs, a **personalised support assessment** should be conducted from the outset. This involves identifying specific requirements, such as transportation assistance or communication aids, to remove barriers to participation and ensure that every individual can fully engage in the deliberation.

Recommendations for Inclusive Process Design

Incorporating **participant inclusion in process design** is vital for addressing the expectations, needs, and potential barriers faced by vulnerable groups. By involving these groups from the very beginning, organizers can tailor the process to be more responsive and accessible, ultimately leading to better outcomes and greater participant satisfaction.

By combining these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can be designed to empower individuals, accommodate diverse needs, and create opportunities for meaningful engagement for all participants, particularly those from vulnerable communities.

4.1.2. Event duration, frequency and time planning:

General Advice:

This section thematizes good practices and guiding ideas for the issues of event frequency, event duration and time planning. First of all, it is important to mention that time stands out as one of the main barriers to participation, as mentioned by a OECD report from 2009: "... when the OECD asked governments from 25 countries and the European Commission which of these principles were the hardest to apply, 45% of respondents cited a lack of resources, and 36% cited time factors (OECD, 2009 Focus on Citizens: Public Engagement for Better Policy and Services). A lack of time and resources was similarly one of the most common barriers to enacting inclusion identified by participants in the Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue's 2019 focus groups on inclusion in public engagement." (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 23). Addressing the barrier of limited temporal resources properly entails giving participants the feeling that the time spent in the process is valued by the organizers and relevant policy-makers and public authorities alike.

Besides limited time resources on the side of participants, events and processes shall spare enough time to accommodate the participants' needs to deliberate on issues which raise their attention and are of interest to them. As stated in the following quote, organizers are called to spare enough time to enable deeper discussions on issues of a commonly shared relevance "... rather than rushing through something that clearly holds meaning. Providing compensation also shows consideration and respect for participants' time and wellbeing." (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 29). As argued in the same publication (ibid.: 23) participative processes planned and implemented without an adequate amount of resources (human, time, information, etc.), risk causing harm to organizers, commissioners and participants alike.

Another point referring to time or more concretely, to timing, links up to the policy cycle. A very basic question guiding every team of organizers before involving citizens in a participatory process is the question whether the process is in any sense linked to the temporal frame of a decision-making cycle. "There is enough time to organise a participatory process, and the time frame fits the decision-making cycle. Meaning that the decision has not been taken before the process starts." (OECD 2022: 21). This quote points at the importance of avoiding a participatory process which does not promise any substantial impact on actual decision-making processes because it is not linked temporally to any decision-making process.

The question of how many events shall be organized together making up a participatory process is inevitably linked to the choice of formats (see for 4.1.7.). Referring to Escobar's and Elstub's overview of mini-public formats (Escobar/Elstub 2017: 4) and our factsheets in deliverable 4.1. (ibid.: p. 33-47), one can see the usual duration of a series of commonly used formats. A very popular deliberative format such as the Citizen Jury usually takes 3 to 5 days and following up on Escobar's and Elstub's overview, other deliberative formats usually stretch over several days, with Citizen Assemblies being most resource-intensive with a usual duration between 20 to 30 days. On the other hand, there are methods, which are more rooted in co-creative practices, such as LEGO serious play, image guided exchanges of experiences or citizen exhibitions. These methods have a shorter duration but they can also not be considered as deliberative formats, with clear deliberative sessions and an outcome to be fed into policy-making processes.

In a nutshell: depending on the choice of formats, the frequency of events can be determined. More guiding information on the choice of formats and methods can be found in section 4.1.7 and 4.1.8. .

The last point to be presented here is that of preparing a timeline, which describes all the steps necessary to implement a participatory process from the early preparation stage to the stage after deliberation. Depending on the choice of formats and/or methods and the envisaged scale, participatory processes can take several weeks to several months in total. An effective implementation necessitates to detail time plans as early as possible.

First, organizers shall be aware of the fact that the implementation of deliberative formats usually consumes a lot of time, e.g. "...for a deliberative process, several months are required to get stakeholders and decision makers on board, around two months to conduct a process of random selection of participants, and several months of learning and deliberation of participants (as they meet every or every other weekend)." (OECD 2022: 57). Second, organizers should make a clear choice regarding the formats and methods to be implemented.

Third, organizers shall determine the frequency of single events. For example a process could be made up by a pre-training event, an information event, an event for deliberative sessions and one final event to present the outcomes to policy-makers. In this example there would be four events making up a participatory process. Fourth, organizers shall consider the length of breaks between the events. If an event necessitates a long preparation time (e.g. because of reaching out and consulting experts or preparing information material) breaks between events would be

longer. A risk to be managed is that long breaks between an information event and a successive deliberative event risks that participants forget relevant information. The example shows that breaks between a series of events belonging to a participative process should be carefully planned, bearing in mind that participants are probably not engaged with the issue at hand during breaks and thus, that information may have to be presented and discussed anew, which again consumes time.

Fifth, it is important to create detailed time and moderation plans for each event. These moderation plans shall contain all information about the length of each point on the agenda, breaks, needed materials and responsibilities in the team of organizers. It should also contain bad case scenarios and sketch out detailed contingency plans in a constructive way. Such scenarios could be that a participant has health problems, that participants feel uncomfortable with the process and refuse to be actively engaged or that policy-makers (or unexpected external events) change some of the very conditions the process was based on. Sixth, organizers shall align the time frame of the participatory process with the time frame of a decision-making cycle (see also for 4.1.3.). And finally, seventh, in case vulnerable groups participate, it is important to accommodate the pace of an event, that is, the number and length of breaks as well as the density and complexity of information and inputs, to the specific needs of vulnerable groups.

Evolvement of discussions throughout the design stage:

Initially, the partners discussed varying event durations based on survey feedback, with some favoring longer sessions for deeper engagement. However, after the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, it became evident that more frequent, shorter sessions were favored for maintaining participant motivation and engagement.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table):

Bologna	The process involves preparatory meetings and deliberation-focused sessions. It is an iterative process leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the topics. There will be 5 to 6 events based on the scope to calibrate the process according to the participants needs. The duration of the individual meetings can vary from 2 to 3 hours approximately.
Madrid	The sessions are structured around a series of five work phases, each session lasting about three hours. This allows for in-depth discussions on the topics and thorough consideration of different viewpoints.
Barcelona	The sessions are shorter but more frequent, with four two-hour sessions planned. This structure allows for more flexible participation and shorter, focused engagements. Additionally, participants will be able to contact each other through an online chat between in-person sessions.

Commonality	While all pilots involve multiple sessions, the frequency and duration differ, with Bologna focusing on preparatory events, Madrid on extended working phases, and Barcelona opting for shorter, more frequent sessions.
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Recommendations from 4.1. to enhance inclusivity:

To enhance participatory processes, careful design and thorough preparation are essential. By incorporating tools and recommendations that prioritize inclusivity, flexibility, and engagement, organizers can create environments that empower participants, particularly those from vulnerable groups.

Tools and Methods for Process Design and Preparation

An **extended preparation period** is crucial for laying the foundation for an inclusive process. This dedicated time frame allows for trust-building activities, individualized support assessments, and pre-engagement workshops. These steps ensure participants feel comfortable, informed, and ready to engage.

Selecting an **accessible and inclusive location** is another vital consideration. Venues such as community centers, which are both physically and culturally accessible, help foster a sense of belonging and comfort for all participants. Additionally, engaging **human resources for support**, such as skilled facilitators, interpreters, logistical staff, and inclusivity teams, ensures that vulnerable participants receive the assistance they need to participate fully.

Recommendations for Inclusive Design

Involving **participant inclusion in process design** from the outset is a key recommendation for addressing the expectations, needs, and potential barriers of vulnerable groups. Their input ensures that the process is tailored to be as inclusive and effective as possible.

Flexible timelines and contingency plans should be built into the process design to accommodate the diverse needs of participants. This flexibility allows organizers to adjust the pace of events, arrange additional workshops, and provide long-term engagement opportunities for those requiring extra support.

Creating an **inclusive environment** is equally important. Accessible and comfortable spaces with thoughtful seating arrangements can encourage open dialogue and minimize power dynamics. This fosters an atmosphere of equality and respect, enabling participants to engage more meaningfully.

Finally, prioritizing **long-term and regular engagement** is essential for building trust, familiarity, and consistency. By scheduling multiple engagement events over time, organizers can strengthen relationships with participants and ensure ongoing involvement in the process.

By implementing these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can become more inclusive, adaptable, and empowering, ensuring that all participants feel valued and able to contribute effectively

4.1.3. Expected Outcomes

General Advice:

Expected outcomes of a participatory process are the envisaged outcomes of the inputs participants provide to the policy cycle throughout the process. The OECD distinguishes three expected outcomes of the inputs: “The expected outcome of the inputs gathered through a participatory process can vary from informative purposes (information) or a consultative exercise (consultation), to more impactful outcomes, potentially with binding results (engagement).” (OECD 2022: 25). A guideline referring to the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) suggests more differentiated distinctions, such as inform, consult, involve, collaborate and empower (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 8). The difference between involving and collaborating is that collaborating with citizens entails that citizens actively co-produce solutions to shared problems and that the citizens’ advice is being incorporated “...to the maximum extent possible.” (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 8), whereas involving does not imply such a strongly committed consideration of citizens’ input into the development of new policies.

Which inputs can participation processes provide for policy-making? Inputs can be manifold: hundreds of online-questionnaires’ results, a joint statement written by a group of randomly selected citizens or a prototype of technological innovation. The outcomes of these inputs in a policy-making process cannot be foreseen by anyone, as there are too many factors in play (conflicting interests, parties, expertises or limited resources for example). However, organizers shall have a strategy concerning the question when and by whom the input(-s) are going to be picked up and further considered. As a matter of accountability and the building of realistic expectations (OECD 2022: 68) this should also be communicated to the participants as early as possible. “Even when there is a will to implement findings, action may be obstructed by contradicting policies, limited resources, or turnover in staff and leadership. Sometimes, implementation takes years and progress may not be immediately apparent. A lack of periodic updates or benchmarks for measuring change can create the appearance of poor accountability.” (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 20).

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

Following the discussions held at the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, there was a consensus that these outcomes should not only include documentation of findings but also emphasize actionable insights for enhancing the inclusion of vulnerable groups in deliberative processes, broadening the impact on civic engagement.

Bologna	The outcome is expected to be a recommendation report, with additional knowledge generated on the inclusion of vulnerable groups in deliberative processes. The project also aims to build insights into deliberative democracy for the participants.
Madrid	The pilot will produce a recommendation report, with Las Rozas' local government present to listen to participants' recommendations. The outcomes are expected to feed directly into local policy.
Barcelona	A recommendation document is expected, focusing on testing barriers and strategies for moderators in unequal deliberations. The process will also assess the quality of engagement and feedback from participants.
Comparison	All pilots aim to produce recommendation reports, which will encapsulate the insights and conclusions from the deliberative processes.

4.1.4. Choice of Topics

General Advice:

The choice of the topic or problem to be discussed during the process is important as the thematic focus relates participatory processes to other forms of political or social engagement with the topic or problem, or more broadly, to the general public sphere. Two points are of particular interest and should be kept in mind: first, the definition and framing of the problem determines the ways participants will engage with it; second, the choice of a topic or problem to be discussed shall be made with respect to its current position within the policy or decision-making cycle.

Regarding the first point, organizers should be well aware that "...poorly defined problems [are] much more difficult to solve, as the way a problem or situation is understood and framed has an impact on the range and types of possible solutions (OECD, 2019[4])." (OECD 2022: 23). In order to arrive at a definition which is clear enough to be discussed by citizens in a constructive way, organizers and public authorities shall ask themselves a series of questions. The overarching question is, whether the topic or problem to be discussed is well-defined or at least definable for lay people. If there is certainty about the topic or problem the question arises, whether the problem is likely to stay the same throughout the participatory process. For example, if the topic is a fast-changing emerging technology (e.g. autonomous driving or blockchains), it may be that basic conditions regarding the topic change during the participatory process. If so, it is up to the organizers and commissioners of the process (and the experts they consult) to assess whether they can frame and compartmentalize the problem or topic in a way that possible changes of the topic or problem during the participatory process do not affect the process.

Further, organizers shall ask themselves, whether there are already generally accepted solutions to the problem at stake and how they will refer to these solutions during the process. The same

applies to previous (failed or successful) attempts in solving the problem. These attempts can serve as examples for best or worst practices and may enrich the discussions. Finally, organizers shall have a clear idea of the contribution they are expecting from the participants regarding the solution of the problem or the topic. Are participants supposed to develop (new) solutions? Or shall they assess and evaluate already existing solutions? Or is the aim to make participants comment and provide feedback on prototypes, imagined solutions or more broadly, visions. All these questions (OECD 2022: 23) may help organizers to frame the topic or problem in a way that fits the expectations of the organizers towards the contributions of the participants.

The second point of relevance here concerns the policy or decision-making cycle, which is a concept to grasp the journey of an issue from its problematization to finding a solution and finally evaluating it and so on. The OECD (2022) defines five stages of a policy cycle: issue identification, policy formulation, decision making, implementation and evaluation. Organizers of a participatory process shall take into account in which stage of the policy cycle the topic at heart of the participatory process is or would be. For example, a city's government puts forward a plan to privatize its public water infrastructure. Newspapers report on these plans and a growing number of citizens join an informal citizen's movement taking place on social media and chat groups but also in real life as protests emerge and gatherings.

In reaction to this, the city's fictional government in our story decides to start a participatory process, in which a representative sample of the city's population chosen by sortition and experts will co-create one or more future visions for the city's water infrastructure. In this case, the city has chosen the topic ("future visions for the city's water infrastructure"), the formats and the methods (random sampling, representativity, co-creation) according to the issue's current stage within the policy cycle, the policy formulation stage. The example illustrates the interrelation between the choice of a topic for a participatory process and the topic's stage in the policy cycle. It should be added that the same topic (e.g. climate change) can be part of different policy cycles depending on, for example, the choice of the spatial scale the issue is framed within. Organizers shall be aware of these interrelations when choosing a topic and its framing.

Stage in the Policy Cycle	Issue Identification Stage	Policy Formulation Stage	Decision-making stage	Implementation stage	Evaluation Stage
Exemplary Participatory and Deliberative Formats of citizen engagement	Representative Deliberative Processes; Citizen Initiatives, etc	Co-Creation; Co-Design; workshops; feedback sessions, etc	Participatory Budgets; Deliberative Processes combined with a referendum, etc	Open innovation labs; Open Spaces; Recurrent public meetings, etc	Polls; surveys; Participative evaluations, etc

*Table 2 Overview of Policy Stages and corresponding participatory formats
(Source: OECD 2022: 24 and own elaboration)*

Evolvement of discussions throughout the design stage:

The partners did not change their minds concerning the choice of topics, they agreed on the importance of choosing topics that are relevant to the lives of participants.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	The topics chosen are connected to everyday issues that participants face. This ensures relevance and engagement, as participants can directly relate to the subjects under discussion. The choice of the topic is still being discussed between the Municipality of Bologna and the project team of the Bologna pilot.
Madrid	The topics are selected in collaboration with the Las Rozas municipality, ensuring that they are aligned with local government priorities and community needs. The city council collaborates in selecting the topic, reflecting the top-down nature of the process. We prefer a topic that is not directly tied to the participants' social backgrounds. Additionally, we aim to frame the topic in a way that connects global issues to local contexts. For instance, participants can deliberate on local concerns, such as waste management, through the lens of global challenges like climate change. This approach helps avoid tacit consensus or superficial arguments, such as generic calls for "more and better services," and encourages deeper, higher-quality discussions.
Barcelona	The topics are selected to allow a mix of plenary and group sessions. These include elements of controversy and consensus-building, making the sessions more dynamic and engaging.
Comparison	All pilots ensure the relevance of topics to participants' daily lives, though the selection process varies— Bologna (bottom-up process) emphasizes participant-driven issues, while Madrid (top-down process) and Barcelona (transversal process) include local government and structured debate elements.

4.1.5. Deciding on an appropriate format for the participative process**General Advice:**

As indicated, determining the expected outcome of the inputs of the participation process, defining the target group and an adequate recruitment method and deciding on an issue are interrelated. The fourth key decision interrelated with the aforementioned ones is the decision on the format.

As the overview of the OECD (2022: 30-32) suggests, formats as different as Citizen Science, Public Consultation, Participatory Budgeting, Open Innovation Labs or Representative Deliberative Processes can produce valuable inputs for one or more stages of the policy or decision-making cycle (issue identification, policy formulation, decision making, implementation and evaluation; see also 4.1.3.). But not all formats produce the same type of inputs into the policy or decision-making cycle and corresponding effects. There are different typologies describing the effects of the inputs produced in participatory processes. Put more abstractly, all of these typologies have two extreme poles, with one describing participation as mere information of the citizenry and the other pole describing participative processes leading to an effective engagement of citizens fostering a substantial impact on decision-making. It is clear that a one-size-fits-all recommendation on the choice of the format is not possible, as at least the four aforementioned decisions play a role at the same time, varying from case to case.

One example may illustrate the interdependencies. If public authorities or others in charge of designing a participation process decided that they need representative public feedback on shortcomings of the city's waste resource management units and facilities (policy formulation stage), the city's authorities or NGO's would rather combine public consultation meetings and polls supported by digital participation tools, such as interactive maps to gather data from citizens. To the contrary, if the expected input of the process into the decision-making cycle are concrete recommendations regarding an upcoming or debated political decision such as abortion and climate change in Ireland (2016-2018) or a new line of the metro subway in South Korea (2018) (OECD 2022: 50-51), representative deliberative processes (mini-publics) would be the choice. The choice of the format is thus highly context-dependent.

Choosing formats has implications for the costs of the process. Extensive deliberative processes may entail several weekends of participation throughout a year which creates costs on the side of organizers, as commuting, catering and accommodation shall be covered to minimize financial exclusion. Costs are also produced on the side of participants as they spend their leisure time or take days off to be available. Consultation processes are less cost-intensive but they are also not representative and it can thus be more difficult to legitimize its results as orientation in decision-making cycles. Living Libraries, an interactive storytelling format to reduce stereotypes, for example usually only take one day and usually have no written output documenting the sessions.

Also worth noting that the combination of formats is possible and often useful. A particularly good example for a combination "... was in 2015 in Chile, where the President used a participatory process to draft the constitution. The process was organised in three main stages. Firstly, an online individual questionnaire collected 90,804 responses. Subsequently, local self-governance meetings of 10 to 30 people were held, mostly in private spaces, but also in universities, schools, churches and other community spaces. Finally, more institutionalised participation took place through local cabildos or town council meetings at the provincial and regional levels." (Tomlyova 2024: 8). As the example shows, the combination of formats makes sense insofar each format produces a valuable input for the following format.

Status Quo:

Pilot/ Format	Citizen Juries	World Café	Civic Assemblies	Living Libraries	Focus Groups	Citizen Exhibitions	Participatory Platform: Interactive Digital Forums
Las Rozas, Madrid (Use Case I)	✓	✓					
Italian Cities and Regions (Use Case II)			✓	✓			
Barcelona Ombudsman (Use Case III)					✓	✓	✓

Table 3 Status quo of choices on formats (Own Elaboration)

iDEM Pilot	Participatory Formats	Description	Methods	Tools
Las Rozas, Madrid (Use Case I)	Consultation Platform, Citizen Juries, World Café	This pilot focuses on creating an accessible consultation platform for residents with disabilities and migrants with limited Spanish proficiency. Citizen juries enable structured feedback from small groups, while the World Café allows informal discussions.	Clear explanation of the decision-making process, accessible location, incentives, inclusive recruitment, trusted communication channels, personalized support assessment, small and mixed groups, flexible timelines, inclusive environment, clear and simplified communication, empathetic moderation techniques, collaborative outcome review.	Basic furniture (chairs), paper and pen, printed handouts, projector and screen, video clips, sound equipment (microphone and speakers), sound and video recording equipment (for researchers), Idem as a web service platform (and devices to run it if any participant needs it: tablets?), drive (for researchers), digital space for information (for participants).

iDEM Pilot	Participatory Formats	Description	Methods	Tools
Bologna Italian Cities and Regions (Use Case II)	Mini-Publics, Civic Assemblies, Living Libraries	In Italy, where public deliberations often involve bottom-up participation, mini-publics are a useful format. Between the most common there are civic assemblies that allow broader engagement in structured settings. Living Libraries facilitate storytelling from marginalized groups and can contribute to information emergence and knowledge dissemination.	A modified version - of OST (Open Space Technology) in order to identify the main questions/problems to be addressed in dialogue and deliberation (focus group or moderated small discussion group). Q&A session with topic expert. Voting could be an option.	Digital space for repository of information material and social media channels (like WhatsApp). Screen for presentation, ppt, printed documents summary in easy-to-read version, physical and digital materials to be used during sessions (flipchart, post-it, paper, pens, cards with images, tablets, mic and sound service, camera, audio-recorder, etc...). Gadgets, printed certificates, and food.
Barcelona Ombudsman (Use Case III)	Focus Groups, Citizen Exhibitions, Interactive Digital Forums	This pilot will focus on working on a topic that affects the day-to-day lives of the participants and is related to life in the city of Barcelona. Inspired by the implications of the concept of "universal accessibility", the different participatory sessions will be organized. Some sessions will be plenary (with all participants, elderly people, migrants and people with disabilities) and other sessions will be specific to each group. For discussing issues affecting people with disabilities, focus groups foster in-depth feedback. Citizen exhibitions raise public awareness by showcasing participant contributions, and interactive forums enable ongoing dialogue.	Focus groups, small discussion groups, interactive discussion between people from different groups to promote this interaction and not lose interest between in-person sessions, an app (like Whatsapp or similar chat) will be used through which participants can continue the debate and exchange.	Materials in paper format, and in audiovisual format that will be available both during face-to-face sessions and in the digital environment. It will be guaranteed that all of them are accessible, taking into account the needs of the target audience (clear language, easy reading, sign language, braille, audio description, subtitles, etc.).

Table 4 Comparative Overview on key design features of each pilot

4.1.6. Recruitment Method

General advice:

The recruitment method basically depends on the choice of the target group of the process. Citizen participation processes with a random sampling approach usually target a representative sample of a country's, region's, city's or neighbourhood's population. But there is a range of possible target groups, such as citizens as a non-representative group, citizens as a representative sample of a community, citizens of a specific geographical area, citizens of a sectoral group (youth, elderly, students, indigenous communities, etc.) or stakeholders such as NGOs, unions, universities, grassroots movements, businesses, etc. (OECD 2022: 24).

On a general level, there are three methods to recruit participants: open calls, closed calls and random sampling (or civic lotteries). Open calls are publicly announced calls for participation which are directed at every potential participant interested to participate (self-selection). Sometimes only the registration is open. The organizers can use an open registration for gathering a greater pool of interested citizens and then selecting a final composition with predefined (and openly communicated) criteria. Closed calls are characterized by the fact that politicians, administrations or civil servants deliberately choose and invite selected participants to participate in a process which can combine deliberative and participatory elements. This can be for example a multi-stakeholder process with many different experts and different affected communities in a post-catastrophic scenario of a flood in a specific region. The reasons for the involvement of very specific people can be manifold, such as merit, competence, formal authority, expertise, representativeness of a community, organization or interest group. Civic lotteries or randomly sampled mini-publics are forms of participative processes, in which a pool of potential participants is determined by random sampling and then selected according to predefined criteria, mostly the representativity for a specific community or region. It thereby compensates for the disadvantage of open calls, that is self-selection by mostly those who are "...older, male, well-educated, affluent, white, and urban (Dalton, 2008[6]; Kuser Olsen, Galloway and Ruth, 2018[7]; Smith, Lehman Schlozman and Verba, 2009[8])." (OECD 2022: 27). It also compensates for the disadvantage of closed calls, that is, their potential lack of inclusivity and a potential bias towards powerful individuals, institutions and interest-groups.

Combinations of recruitment methods are also possible, e.g. complementing a randomly sampled representative group of citizens with a group of vulnerable people chosen by a closed call. In any case, the choice of a target group precedes the choice for a or several recruitment method(s). Similarly important is the definition of the envisaged output of the process. For more examples concerning the fit between expected output of the process (or: input into a policy cycle) see the encompassing overview in the OECD's guidelines on deliberative and participatory processes (OECD 2022: 27). It is also important to point at D4.1. because its findings suggest abstaining from random sampling when working with vulnerable groups as findings suggest that random sampling is particularly unsuitable for recruiting vulnerable groups.

Discussions:

Initially, the recruitment methods varied significantly across pilots, with a focus on digital platforms and local organizations. After the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, discussions emphasized the need for more structured recruitment methods, particularly in Madrid and Barcelona, which seek to enhance inclusivity by engaging specific demographic groups through established community networks and organizations.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Recruitment is conducted mainly through local organizations, social media, and video campaigns. The focus is on reaching participants through digital platforms and community networks or possibly digital platforms. Communication will take place through dedicated social media groups, calls, mails or other project digital spaces. In particular, the recruitment method for the target group of migrants is still being discussed between the Municipality of Bologna and the pilot's project team.
Madrid	Recruitment emphasizes the intersectionality of participants, focusing on gender balance and engaging local associations. The goal is to ensure a representative group by partnering with organizations that serve different demographic groups. Recruitment will be carried out through subcontracting to another organization called 'Las Rozas Innova.', a municipal public company with extensive experience in innovation management and participation.
Barcelona	Recruitment is coordinated through civil society and academia, with the involvement of NGOs and support persons. This approach ensures ongoing contact with participants, even in phases without face-to-face interaction. Synergy with the entities that have already participated during the Focus Group and the interviews of T 5.1 will be key. Through the facilitators of these entities, contact will be made with the people who are usually part of the Participation Councils or are motivated in the topic.
Comparison	All three pilots rely on partnerships with local organizations and civil society to ensure effective recruitment and communication. However, Madrid and Barcelona put a stronger emphasis on structured collaboration with specific associations and academic institutions.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity:

To improve participatory processes, it is essential to design and implement recruitment strategies that effectively reach and engage vulnerable or marginalized groups. These strategies should focus on inclusivity, trust-building, and the use of tailored incentives to motivate participation.

Tools and Methods for Effective Recruitment

Tailored recruitment strategies are key to connecting with vulnerable groups. These strategies can include partnerships with community organizations, door-to-door outreach, and personalized engagement efforts. By using methods specifically designed to address the unique barriers faced by these groups, organizers can ensure that participation opportunities are accessible and appealing.

Providing **incentives** is another important method for motivating participation. Material incentives, such as salaries or transportation reimbursements, can alleviate financial and logistical barriers, while non-material incentives, such as opportunities for skill-building or public recognition, provide additional motivation and validation for participants.

Recommendations for Inclusive Recruitment

Adopting **inclusive recruitment strategies** is critical to reaching groups that may not respond to conventional methods. These strategies should prioritize the needs of vulnerable or marginalized populations, ensuring that they are actively included in the process.

Using **trusted communication channels** further enhances the effectiveness of recruitment efforts. Collaborating with familiar community organizations or advocates allows organizers to engage participants through channels they already know and trust, particularly those who have limited experience with civic processes. This approach helps build confidence and fosters initial engagement.

By implementing these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can become more accessible, inclusive, and effective, ensuring that all voices, especially those from vulnerable groups, are represented and heard.

4.1.7. Group Size

General Advice:

There are no standardized group sizes for deliberative or participative events. The size of the overall group of participating citizens depends on the choice of formats. Typical formats of deliberative participation (mini-publics in the narrow sense) range from 12-26 for the case of Citizens' Juries to 100-160 people for the case of Citizens' Assemblies (Escobar/Elstub 2017: 4). An image guided exchange of ideas normally takes place with up to 25 participants. In a neighbourhood walk up to 15 people per group take part and in a citizen's exhibition up to 50 people. Small group discussions usually take place with 4 to 6 people.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

The partners did not change their minds concerning group size, with some pilots prioritizing variety and inclusion, while others prioritize smaller groups to foster interaction.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	The size of the participant group adheres to established numbers from the proposals (meaning 25 persons with intellectual disabilities and optional 15 with migratory background), ensuring manageable group dynamics for meaningful deliberation.
Madrid	The composition of the group is determined in the Doinf of Action: 15-20 migrants, 15-20 intellectually disabled, 15-20 seniors. We have decided not to preventively reduce the number of participants. We will seek to do so with the committed figures and will only reduce them if there are problems in recruitment or some other unexpected (but never planned) issue.
Barcelona	Small groups (6 to 8 participants) are emphasized to foster focused interaction. A challenge of mixing participants with differing levels of expertise is acknowledged but addressed through moderation and facilitation. The sessions may be in small format (when the attendees belong only to one group) or plenary (when all the participants, migrants, elderly people or people with intellectual disabilities discuss together). The size of the group will depend, being in the first case 6-8 people and in the second case 18-24 members.
Comparison	All pilots deal with the challenge of group size, seeking to balance inclusivity with effectiveness. Bologna and Barcelona opt for smaller groups, while Madrid is exploring how to manage larger participation effectively.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity :**Recommendations:**

Decide whether to create homogeneous (homogeneous vulnerable groups only) or mixed settings, carefully balancing different needs.

4.1.8. Usage of digital tools, the iDEM service and testing**General Advice:**

The usage of digital tools, such as discussion platforms, video chats, messenger services or specific apps and digital voting tools may enhance the participation of groups of citizens, which experience mobility barriers or which are hard to reach with analogue means, such as young people. Tools like video chats, digital mind-maps and gamified digital gathering spaces can

substantially contribute to reducing the costs of participative processes as costly long commutes, facilities, hotels and catering cease to be paid for. A different exemplary case is Criminal Court No. 10 in Buenos Aires, Argentina, which leverages digital tools to foster an open justice system. The court actively collects, publishes, and shares rulings and decisions via social media platforms. Moreover, it maintains an open data repository and a publicly accessible open-code dashboard featuring visualizations of the collected data. This innovative approach not only enhances transparency but also promotes public engagement in the judicial process (Tomlyova 2024). The OECD strongly encourages the usage of open source tools as "... evidence shows that open-source software is best suited for democratic processes because it allows for scrutiny, accountability, and collaboration." (OECD 2022: 51).

These aforementioned examples may show that (open source) digital tools can be a helpful supplement to participatory processes when they are introduced with a clear purpose in mind which fits the overall purposes of the process. A typical trade-off when using digital tools in participatory processes is caused by the promise of a higher inclusivity by the usage of tools which may be achieved at the cost of fewer opportunities for face-to-face deliberation or too much time needed to let participants learn how to use the tools effectively. It is important to keep in mind that the "digital divide", that is, the unequal distribution of digital competencies, is also a key factor in participative processes (OECD 2022: 51). If possible, participative processes taking place mainly via digital tools and spaces should offer opportunities for offline participation to reproduce exclusionary effects of the 'digital divide' in the participation process. "Think about those that do not have access to the internet or to digital devices. If possible, always provide an offline alternative to participate. Non-digital alternatives can be, for example: physical voting, consultations via phone, or any other in-person mechanisms (workshops, kiosks, paper mail, etc.)." (OECD 2022: 58).

Finally, using digital tools for making participation fun or gamifying participation may "... motivate citizens to get involved. The look, feel, and interface of digital tools used is also important to make the process appealing." (OECD 2022: 29). This points at the need for participative technology development (Aschenbrenner et al 2024: 9) and UX-testing, which will also be at the centre of T 4.4. .

Following up on that, the iDEM service will be tested as an assistive tool in selected situations of the participative process, in which the iDEM tool promises to alleviate barriers normally occurring in these situations. The situations of concern will be chosen by those in charge of the pilots, who (with other partners) will refine their strategy for testing the app after conducting pre-trainings. However, organizers shall also be aware of the possibility that participants may wish or decide to use the app in situations, in which it is not expected to be used. It can thus become a challenge for moderators to direct the attention of the participants to the app or away from it.

Concerning pre-training and its linkage to testing, the need for prior training of participants is normally not given. Every participative process has an information phase, in which the

participants get information on the issue and the process itself. Pre-training with participants (no matter if from vulnerable groups or not) will contribute to a better experience with the tool during the following pilots. The question arises: on what should the testing and evaluation of the tool in the pilots focus? If it should focus on the *first* user interaction and the ways users make sense of the app on a general level, pre-training should not be provided or only to a very limited extent. If it should focus on testing user interaction with a focus on the interaction of users with the app and *situated within* the overall participative process, some training on how to use the app and what its functions and limits are should be provided. It should be kept in mind that prior training is one element of the information phase, as providing information on the issue and the process itself are as well. Organizers will have to find a balance between properly informing and training and not ever adding too much complexity to the participants' experiences of the participative process and its actual purpose(s) for them and the overall community.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

At the time of the survey, there were concerns regarding the understanding and integration of the iDEM service among participants. The participatory design workshop in Barcelona prompted a stronger commitment to prior training sessions across all pilots, ensuring that both participants and facilitators are adequately equipped to utilize the iDEM app effectively, thus enhancing overall engagement in the participatory processes.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	The process will consist of the following steps: participants recruitment; preparation; information phase; dialogue/deliberation phase; evaluation. The iDEM services will be mainly integrated in the information phase. The process will also use a digital space. The possibilities considered for the development of the digital space are Decidim or Wordpress. The final answer to this question still has to be figured out between the pilot's project team and the company
Madrid	The iDEM app will be used as an assistance tool in situations of offline deliberation. There is a need for better knowledge of the app's functions, and pre-training is recommended to ensure that participants can effectively engage with iDEM. As the DoA specifies in Task 4.5.1.3. iDEM will be used as a "web platform" used as a "reading facilitator" by providing easy-to-read translations of the documents. In addition, the pilot's project team considers the possibility of extending the deliberation between sessions using an online tool to facilitate the preparation of the sessions and the engagement of the participants (as Barcelona intends to do). In that case, iDEM could also be used in a participatory online setting.
Barcelona	The iDEM service will be used throughout all phases of the participatory process, making this pilot the most ambitious in terms of fully integrating

	<p>the app into the workflow. We intend for the app to be used and tested by both technical teams and participants.</p> <p>The technicians will use it to prepare easy-to-read documentation prior to the participatory sessions.</p> <p>The participants will test and evaluate it during the participatory sessions.</p>
<p>Commonality</p>	<p>Each pilot plans to use the iDEM service to facilitate participation, though all three face challenges in understanding its full potential and functionalities and in figuring out the most promising scenarios for its usage.</p>

4.2. During the main participatory process

4.2.1. Managing Tiredness and Participant Motivation

General Advice:

The primary motive for citizens to participate in participatory processes should be the opportunity to influence decision-making. But there are additional measures that make participation more accessible, rewarding, and engaging. Public authorities or others in charge can adopt various strategies to reduce barriers and foster inclusivity, ensuring that participants stay motivated throughout the process and feel that their investment of time, effort and trust is being valued.

One approach is to provide *tangible support to participants*. Financial compensation for expenses such as transportation, childcare, or digital tools can lower practical barriers, while financial rewards like honoraria or vouchers offer a direct incentive for participation. For in-person events, offering childcare services or support for vulnerable groups, such as accessible facilities or sign language interpretation, ensures that more citizens can engage without facing undue challenges. It has to be considered that people with intellectual disabilities, as one out of three target groups with communication access needs, are not a homogenous group. There are different stages of intellectual disabilities distinguished by different organizations. For the context of the project, we can state that all pilots will probably invite only participants with a mild or lower intellectual disability. Further, organizers should be aware of their local, regional and cultural specificity of being a disabled person, e.g. the fact that a relevant portion of deaf people in Italy do not speak sign language for ideological reasons.

Beyond practical support, participatory processes can be designed to be *socially and personally enriching*. Creating opportunities for social interaction fosters a sense of community and belonging, while gamification and appealing digital tools can make the process more enjoyable. Recognizing participants’ contributions through certificates or public acknowledgment reinforces their civic value, and offering informative experiences or skill-building opportunities makes participation more compelling. Clear communication, including FAQs and process details, can also ease apprehensions and make participation feel approachable for those less familiar with civic engagement. Together, these measures (OECD 2022: 29) demonstrate a commitment to

inclusivity and engagement, ideally motivating citizens to take part throughout the whole process.

Evolvement of discussions throughout the design stage:

Participant fatigue was not explicitly addressed in the survey, however, during the participatory design workshop in Barcelona it was agreed that it is important to avoid participant fatigue by using incentives or proper pacing.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	To avoid participants fatigue, informal moments and breaks are built into the process. Non-financial incentives such as certificates, T-shirts, and food are also provided to maintain engagement.
Madrid	The design incorporates insights from previous studies (e.g., barriers to participation, intersectionality). Sufficient time is provided to avoid fatigue, and participants are offered opt-out options. Economic incentives are also used to maintain motivation, and simple roles help participants stay focused on specific tasks.
Barcelona	Limiting session time and using easy language in all materials are key strategies to prevent tiredness. The process alternates between plenary and group discussions to keep participants engaged. Furthermore, to maintain attention during the sessions, we will ensure that the sessions are dynamic, that everyone has a clear structure and that they feel challenged by the topic of debate at all times.
Comparison	All pilots recognize the need to avoid participants fatigue. Bologna and Madrid rely on incentives (financial or otherwise), while all three pilots ensure proper pacing and alternation between activities to maintain motivation.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity :

To ensure inclusive and meaningful participation, it is essential to adapt the pace and structure of deliberative processes to accommodate the diverse needs of participants. Slowing down discussions, allowing time for reflection, and maintaining flexibility are key strategies to foster thoughtful engagement and equitable participation.

Tools and Recommendations

One effective strategy is to **adapt the deliberation pace** by slowing down discussions. This approach encourages thoughtful reflection and careful listening, ensuring that all participants, including those who may need more time to process information, have the opportunity to contribute. Slower-paced discussions also help reduce the influence of dominant voices, creating a more balanced and inclusive dialogue.

It is crucial to **provide ample time for reflection**, avoiding short, intensive sessions that may overwhelm participants or limit their ability to process complex topics. Allowing sufficient time for participants to absorb information and articulate their views fosters a more thoughtful and meaningful exchange of ideas.

A **flexible approach** to participatory processes is essential for supporting participants with varying needs. Adaptive methods, such as extending timelines or incorporating additional workshops, ensure that those requiring extra time or assistance can fully engage. This flexibility not only accommodates individual needs but also enhances the overall inclusivity and effectiveness of the process.

By implementing these strategies, participatory processes can become more inclusive, thoughtful, and equitable, ensuring that all participants have the time and space needed to contribute meaningfully to the discussion.

4.2.2. Tools to Ensure Trust and a Respectful Atmosphere

General Advice:

To create inclusive and impactful participatory processes, it is essential to address the needs of vulnerable groups by incorporating their specific requirements into the process design. This includes acknowledging and accommodating these needs to ensure equitable access and meaningful engagement for all participants. Additionally, the process must clearly outline the expected contributions from participants and their potential influence on policy-making. Transparency is key: organizers should communicate how, when, and by whom the results will be integrated into the policy cycle, specifying the form, language, and level of detail required. It is equally important to explain why certain recommendations were adopted and others were not, as emphasized by the OECD, organizers and policy-makers shall communicate why some of the recommendations were picked up and others were not (OECD 2022: 25; 60).

Facilitators play a crucial role in fostering a respectful and inclusive environment. They should be trained to handle conflicts and address instances of discriminatory or dehumanizing behavior, such as the usage of sexist, classist, racist, ableist, or homophobic language. As noted by the Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue, moderators must be prepared to manage such challenges effectively to maintain a productive and respectful dialogue (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 16).

Building reciprocal relationships with communities is foundational to equitable public engagement. According to the Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue, “Equitable public engagement is founded on trusting, respectful, collaborative and reciprocal relationships with communities. Dedicate time and resources to relationship building and share power to co-create mutually beneficial and accessible engagement processes” (2020: 15). This can mean to spend more time, human resources and attention on personal and informal interaction, story-telling sessions or playful interaction.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

Survey responses emphasized the importance of moderators and facilitators to create safe, inclusive spaces while enforcing rules of engagement. These points were revisited during the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, where partners refined their approaches. The consensus reflected a commitment to structured, respectful interactions tailored to each pilot's needs.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Trust is built through the roles of moderators and facilitators, who ensure a safe space by mixing different formats. Clear guidelines for experts in the information phase and active involvement in the deliberation are essential for maintaining a constructive atmosphere.
Madrid	Trust is fostered by strict speaking turns and enforcement of courtesy rules. Expulsion is an option if these rules are violated. The pilot avoids too many large group sessions. Instead it mixes homogeneous groups to gradually build trust over time. To foster trust in the organization, one important thing is choosing the optimal method to record participation: very intrusive (video), relatively intrusive (audio), or not very intrusive (notes). Be as it may, data protection policy and informed consent will be designed and implemented. The final choice of the optimal recording method is still being discussed.
Barcelona	Moderation and time control are key to ensuring that participants stick to discussion rules. The diversity of the group is valued, and facilitators play an important role in maintaining structure and order. Emphasis will be placed on mutual respect and on explaining at the start of each session that we must remember that all people are different, we express ourselves differently and at different rhythms.
Comparison	All pilots employ moderators to maintain a constructive and trusting environment. Emphasis is placed on enforcing participation rules and the clear definition of roles. Bologna will additionally use facilitators to enable the mixing of different formats.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity :

To improve participatory processes, several tools and recommendations can be implemented to foster inclusivity, enhance communication, and create a supportive environment for all participants, particularly those from vulnerable groups. These measures focus on effective facilitation, tailored communication, and building a sense of belonging.

Tools and Methods for Effective Participation

Moderated small group discussions are essential for creating a safe and supportive environment where vulnerable individuals feel comfortable expressing themselves. Skilled facilitators can manage these discussions to ensure that all voices are heard and respected. To further enhance understanding and independent learning, **prepared handouts and glossaries** should be provided. These materials, including booklets or glossaries with key terms, allow participants to consult information at their own pace.

Activities such as **icebreakers and role-playing games** are effective for building interpersonal connections among participants. These activities help create an inclusive and collaborative atmosphere, prioritizing relationships and mutual respect over purely rational decision-making. For participants with specific needs, **flexible and adaptive discussion structures** can be implemented. Extending discussion time or offering sensory-based workshops ensures that individuals with moderate and hopefully severe disabilities can participate meaningfully. Tools like **Talking Mats** also play a vital role in assisting individuals with intellectual disabilities to express their preferences and opinions clearly.

To provide additional support, a **buddy system** can be introduced. Allowing participants to bring trusted individuals for translation, emotional support, or assistance enhances their comfort and encourages active engagement.

Recommendations for Inclusive Participation

Small group settings should be promoted, as they create a more supportive and less intimidating environment. These settings encourage open expression, particularly for vulnerable participants who may feel overwhelmed in larger groups.

Structured and inclusive moderation is critical for ensuring that all participants feel valued and safe. Skilled moderators can provide structure, non-judgmental guidance, and empathetic facilitation to address the challenges faced by participants. Demonstrating **empathy in moderation** is equally important, as moderators need to understand and address both visible and invisible barriers to participation.

Finally, fostering a **sense of belonging** is key to creating a collaborative and inclusive environment. Prioritizing interpersonal connections and mutual respect helps participants feel more engaged and valued, enhancing their overall experience in the participatory process. By integrating these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can become more inclusive and effective, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their circumstances, have the opportunity to contribute meaningfully

4.2.3. Accessibility of Expert Information

General Advice:

Expert knowledge plays a vital role in participatory processes, ensuring that citizens can engage meaningfully with complex issues. While experts possess in-depth experience and knowledge

acquired over years, evidence shows that citizens are capable of understanding and addressing complexity when given adequate time and resources to learn. To support this, experts should help curate, prepare, and present diverse and balanced information, enabling participants to make informed recommendations. Just as decision-makers like parliamentarians rely on technical experts for guidance on complex topics, citizens in participatory processes should have access to similar expertise to inform their contributions (OECD 2022: 17).

Effective participatory processes also integrate both expert knowledge and the practical knowledge of local communities. The complexity of the issues being addressed should shape the design of these processes, including the number of participants, the time allocated, the selection of experts, and the use of digital tools. Experts with experience in designing representative deliberative processes are essential for making these strategic decisions (OECD 2022: 83). This integration not only enriches the deliberative process but also empowers citizens to influence decisions affecting their lives, acting as representatives for broader communities across diverse regions (Tomlyova 2024: 5).

The processing and reproduction of expert knowledge *by experts* involves by definition the usage of technical terms. However, if experts use a myriad of technical terms when engaging with laypeople, this poses an additional communicative challenge. It is not only that technical terms and underlying concepts may be unknown to participants, experts may also have personal opinions and preferences, which are not part of their core expertise but may play a role in their judgement.

The line between pure technical advice and advice based on personal experiences and preferences is fuzzy and can be difficult to determine for citizens not familiar with the issue at stake. It is therefore recommended to encourage experts to use a language which does not unnecessarily create additional barriers besides the usage of technical terms and concepts which cannot be avoided and have to be explained. It is further recommended that experts should be briefed to frame personal opinions as such and to delineate them from their core expertise. Written expert advice could be simplified by experts for easy language or by the usage of digital tools, such as the iDEM service.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

Survey respondents highlighted the necessity for simplifying expert input through multimedia formats, easy-to-read materials, and verbal explanations. During the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, these priorities were integrated into pilot strategies. Across pilots, the shared understanding was that accessible expert information is pivotal for inclusivity and engagement.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Experts are encouraged to simplify their texts and make information accessible during the information deliberation phase. They are expected
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	to be present for Q&A sessions; the project provides guidelines on how to present complex information.
Madrid	Experts are briefed in advance to ensure that their presentations are easy to understand. The process relies on multimedia channels to enhance accessibility, and experts are asked to simplify their texts before presenting, iDEM can be used to do this simplification.
Barcelona	Experts are expected to present information in an easy-to-understand way. Facilitators and supporters are trained in advance to help participants grasp expert input.
Commonality	All pilots emphasize the importance of making expert information accessible. Experts are briefed or guided on how to present complex data in simpler terms to ensure inclusivity.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity:

To ensure effective information sharing in participatory processes, it is essential to use tools and methods that prioritize clarity, accessibility, and relatability. These approaches help participants better understand the topic, foster engagement, and empower them to contribute meaningfully.

Tools and Methods for Effective Information Delivery

Using **multiple communication methods** is crucial to cater to diverse participant needs. Printed handouts, Q&A sessions with experts, presentations, and audio/video content provide a variety of ways for participants to access information. **Easy-to-understand presentations and explanations**, such as short online videos or YouTube clips, can help break down complex topics into more digestible formats, as demonstrated by the Scottish Climate Assembly¹⁸.

To further simplify complex content, **translation applications** like iDEM can translate texts into accessible language in real time, ensuring participants with varying literacy levels can fully engage. Additionally, **adapted information delivery** methods, such as starting sessions with informal discussions to gauge participants' understanding before presenting expert insights, make the learning process more inclusive and effective.

For greater relatability, alternative methods such as **"living libraries"** (where individuals share personal testimonies) and **"experts carousels"** (rotating experts between groups to give concise overviews) can make information more engaging and relatable. Including **personal testimonies**, especially from individuals with disabilities, further enhances the emotional connection to the topic, making it more impactful.

¹⁸

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-climate-assembly-research-report-process-impact-assembly-ember-experience/> (Retrieved at the 20th of December)

Tools for Enhanced Accessibility

Visual tools like **Talking Mats**, which use symbols or pictures, are particularly effective for individuals with intellectual disabilities, helping them articulate their preferences and views. Similarly, **moderation techniques** such as writing responses as bullet points, incorporating visual aids, and using drawings or simplified presentations ensure that even complex topics are accessible and clear.

Recommendations for Improved Information Sharing

Ensuring **clarity and accessibility** is paramount. All information should be presented in clear, jargon-free language and tailored to different literacy and cognitive levels. Easy-to-Read language helps bridge knowledge gaps and makes content accessible to participants with lower literacy levels or intellectual disabilities.

Tailoring information to cognitive levels is another key recommendation. Materials should be adapted to meet the diverse needs of participants, ensuring everyone has an equal opportunity to engage. To further enhance understanding, it is vital to **focus on relatability** by presenting content in ways that connect with participants' personal experiences.

Lastly, encouraging **casual interactions with experts** creates opportunities for informal discussions, fostering engagement and making complex topics easier to comprehend. These interactions help demystify expert knowledge and promote a more collaborative atmosphere. By implementing these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can provide information that is clear, accessible, and relatable, empowering all participants to engage meaningfully in the decision-making process.

4.3. After the main participatory process

4.3.1. Linkage of inputs to Policy-Making

General Advice:

The linkage of the processes' inputs to policy-making is a question which is difficult to answer for all cases as the complexities of policy-making are well-known and differ from case to case. Nonetheless, it is important that organizers of the process clarify three points to arrive at a strategy for linking the inputs stemming from the process to actual decision-making.

First, as indicated in 4.1., organizers shall clarify which kind of input or contribution they suppose citizens to produce. These can be ideas and proposals, broad opinions, expertise or technical advice, informed recommendations, concrete actions to take, feedback or alerts, direct decision or evidence (OECD 2022: 86). Secondly, it should be determined which temporal stage of a

policy-making process these inputs are supposed to feed in and which social arenas, publics or institutional settings are the addressees of these inputs.

Thirdly, organizers should develop strategies to increase pressure on decision-makers in cases where results are disregarded or ignored, and insist that the outcomes are acknowledged and considered. This can be achieved, for instance, by inviting decision-makers to events with participants, where they are required to answer questions about the results or explain in detail which recommendations from the citizens were (or were not) implemented and why.

If evidence suggests that the initial plan to make use of the results does not work anymore because relevant basic conditions have changed, organizers shall immediately inform participants that it may be that their contributions will not be considered the way the organizers had announced it. Participants will then have the choice to continue their engagement under renewed conditions or to withdraw their active participation.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

At the survey stage, the linkage of outcomes to policy-making was vaguely conceptualized. However, the discussions at the participatory design Workshop in Barcelona emphasized the importance of direct engagement with policymakers during and after the events. Partners agreed to organize structured events to ensure that participants' recommendations have a tangible impact on local policy decisions.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Events are organized where policy-makers, participants, and organizers meet to ensure a direct link between recommendations and policy-making. The aim is to create differentiated reports for different audiences, including policy-makers.
Madrid	It is essential for Las Rozas representatives to be present during the event to ensure that participants' recommendations are considered in the local decision-making process. However, the specific mechanism for linking outcomes to policy remains unclear.
Barcelona	When we finish the pilot we will be focused on organizing congresses or events where different stakeholders, including policy-makers, can review the results. There is also an emphasis on sharing findings with other projects and on social media for broader policy relevance.
Comparison	All pilots aim to ensure that the outcomes are communicated to policy-makers through direct engagement events or congresses.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity :

To ensure that participatory processes provide clear, transparent, and effective outcomes, it is essential to adopt tools and recommendations that prioritize accessibility, cultural awareness, and ongoing engagement. These measures foster trust, empower participants, and enhance the impact of their contributions.

Tools and Methods for Clear and Transparent Outcomes

Providing outcomes in **multiple formats**, such as videos, visuals, and written summaries, ensures that diverse audiences can access and understand the results. This approach is complemented by the use of **simplification tools**, such as Easy-to-Read language adaptation applications, which make complex content more accessible, particularly for individuals with lower literacy levels.

To ensure the accuracy and integrity of the outcomes, **collaborative outcome review** can be employed. By involving participants in reviewing and validating the results, organizers can confirm that the findings genuinely reflect the perspectives and contributions of those involved. Additionally, a **clear explanation of the decision-making process** should be provided. Publishing detailed accounts of how decisions were made, and explicitly highlighting where input from vulnerable groups influenced the recommendations reinforce transparency and build trust.

Socio-cultural contextualization is another crucial tool. Partnering with community leaders or organizations familiar with the socio-cultural contexts of vulnerable groups allows communication to be tailored to local norms, enhancing relevance and accessibility. Simple methods, such as follow-up videos or reunion events where officials provide updates on how participants' input has been implemented, further strengthen trust and transparency.

Recommendations for Effective Communication and Engagement

Ensuring **transparency and accessibility** is critical to bridging knowledge gaps and improving understanding. Outcomes should be communicated in accessible language and formats, enabling participants to engage meaningfully with the results. Equally important is demonstrating **respect for cultural contexts** by adapting communication methods to be culturally sensitive. Collaborating with community leaders ensures that the delivery of outcomes aligns with local norms and values.

To empower participants, **recognition of individual contributions** is key. Publicly acknowledging and validating their efforts not only encourages future engagement but also reinforces the value of their input. At the same time, it is important to **manage expectations** during outcome presentations. Preparing participants through appropriate venues, formats, and timing ensures that the process accommodates the needs of target groups and avoids potential disappointment or confusion.

Finally, maintaining **ongoing feedback** channels reinforces transparency and builds confidence in future participatory efforts. Keeping participants informed about how their input is being

utilized fosters a sense of ownership and trust, encouraging continued involvement in civic processes.

By implementing these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can deliver outcomes that are not only clear and transparent but also meaningful and impactful for all stakeholders, particularly vulnerable groups

4.3.2. Communication of Results to Target Groups and Audiences

General Advice:

As recommended by the OECD (2022: 27) organizers shall map their targeted audiences from the outset to identify relevant addressees of the process' inputs to policy-making. A "... mapping exercise can be useful to identify relevant groups of citizens (for example, those affected by the problem to solve) or categories of stakeholders (for example, civil society organisations, businesses, groups of experts etc.) that hold the most relevant experiences, points of view, or expertise." (OECD 2022: 27). In addition, organizers shall map and identify relevant journalists, media outlets or digital spaces to disseminate results publicly.

The communication of outcomes should be tailored to the language and relevance systems of the addressees so that the main messages of the process are being understood in different social worlds and arenas. The point of communicating the results is closely linked to trust in the process: a transparent commitment to communicating results and a clearly defined and communicated scope of the process are key to build trust in the process and manage expectations (Simon Fraser University Morris J. Wosk Centre for Dialogue 2020: 17).

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

Initially, communication strategies varied among pilots, with uncertainty regarding effectiveness. Post-discussion, in the participatory design Workshop in Barcelona, led to a more cohesive communication strategy that prioritizes tailored reporting for different audiences, ensuring that outcomes are effectively disseminated to both policymakers and participants in a meaningful way.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Results will be communicated through differentiated reports for policy-makers and other audiences. The pilot also plans events to present the outcomes directly with the involvement of both groups of participants.
Madrid	Communication of results may occur through email, though there are concerns about whether this method is effective. The communication strategy is still unclear and needs further development.

Barcelona	Results will be shared in specific events with policy-makers, as well as through congresses, social media, and exchanges with other similar projects. Various formats of communication will be used to target different audiences.
Comparison	All pilots recognize the importance of tailoring their communication strategies to different audiences, including policy-makers, participants, and the public.

4.3.3. Updating Participants on Policy Outcomes and fostering long-term engagement

General Advice:

Fostering long-term engagement opportunities is challenging as participatory processes are often commissioned to take place for a specific period of time, to produce inputs for policy-making and to end afterwards so that participants disperse into their private social worlds again. However, as a matter of fostering a culture of participation, organizers and commissioners shall motivate citizens and collect information regarding the questions where and how participants may continue to participate. This can be done by organizing a similar participatory event, polls, public hearings or digital opportunities for participation, such as DM groups, social media or enews. If policy-makers, commissioners or other bodies financing the participatory process do not plan any follow-up activities, the reasons for this should be made transparent and communicated to the participants. It may cause harm to the motivation of participants if the whole process creates the impression that participation is only considered as appropriate and desired for a limited period of time.

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

The survey indicated a lack of clarity on how participants would be updated on policy outcomes. After the participatory design workshop in Barcelona, a framework was established to ensure consistent and clear communication with participants regarding the impact of their contributions, incorporating their preferences for updates into the planning.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Participants will be asked how they would like to stay informed, and an event will be organized where policy-makers and participants come together. This ensures ongoing updates on the policy impact of their recommendations.
Madrid	It remains unclear who will update participants (whether the town hall or project consortium). The communication method and responsibility for updates are still undecided.

Barcelona	Feedback sessions with participants are planned, potentially involving the families of participants as well. Updates will also be shared through congresses and documents tailored to different audiences.
Commonality	All pilots plan to keep participants updated, though the specific mechanisms vary and are more defined in some pilots than others.

Recommendations from deliverable 4.1 to enhance inclusivity:

To enhance inclusivity and foster meaningful participation in public engagement processes, several tools and recommendations can be implemented. These measures aim to create lasting connections, empower participants, and ensure ongoing involvement.

Tools and Methods for Sustained Engagement

Follow-up events play a crucial role in keeping participants engaged after the initial process. These gatherings serve to update participants on developments, celebrate their contributions, and encourage them to remain involved. Similarly, **continuous engagement channels** provide platforms for participants to contribute to future research or advocacy projects, allowing them to act as self-advocates and maintain their connection to civic activities.

To further empower participants, **opportunities for public recognition** can be created. Highlighting individual stories, contributions, or achievements through public acknowledgments or exhibitions reinforces a sense of value and pride among participants. **Citizen exhibitions** are particularly effective, offering a platform for participants to share their insights and experiences publicly, thus strengthening their sense of agency and ownership.

Recommendations for Long-Term Inclusion

Sustained engagement should not end with the completion of a project. **Long-term inclusion beyond the project end** is essential to keep vulnerable groups involved as their recommendations are implemented. Structured opportunities for continued interaction and feedback help ensure that their voices remain influential.

Particularly for socially isolated participants, it is vital to provide **support against social isolation**. Long-term engagement structures create opportunities for meaningful interaction, helping these individuals stay connected and involved. In addition, efforts to **encourage self-advocacy** empower participants to take on active roles in future projects, promoting their sense of agency and reinforcing their value to the community.

Finally, **building sustained trust and connection** is key to fostering long-term involvement. Maintaining open channels for feedback and updates ensures that participants feel heard and valued, encouraging them to stay engaged in civic life and continue contributing to collective goals.

By combining these tools and recommendations, participatory processes can create inclusive, empowering environments that enable lasting engagement and meaningful contributions from all participants.

4.3.4. Indicators for Evaluation

As the OECD suggests following the researcher Tina Nabatchi, it is good to distinguish between process and impact evaluations (OECD 2022: 61). Process evaluations focus on the implementation, its quality and the experiences of participants. It can help public authorities better understand and improve their capacities to implement participatory processes. Impact evaluations focus on whether the process reached its goals. Most importantly, evaluation should be carried out by an external entity. Nexus is strongly involved in research, coordination and design activities and as such, is not in an adequate position to recommend a scheme for evaluation. As a matter of completeness, we list some indicators to be considered in the evaluation of the process, which seem to be relevant from our side:

For process evaluations:

- comparison between initial project plan and the actual process
- process quality, esp. quality of deliberation
- meeting initially defined goals? (referring to the process itself)
- capability to cope with contingencies and problems
- inclusivity
- accessibility
- use of digital tools
- quality of involvement of experts/interaction with experts
- Participants perceptions about the process, its quality, accessibility and whether it has met the expectations

Evolution of discussions throughout the design stage:

During the survey, there was recognition of the need for both qualitative and quantitative evaluation indicators. The participatory design workshop in Barcelona further solidified this understanding, leading to a collaborative agreement on specific indicators that would gauge both participant feedback and the overall effectiveness of the deliberative processes across all pilots.

Status Quo (Design Decisions of each pilot in a table)

Bologna	Quantitative indicators include the number of interactions with the iDEM service, while qualitative indicators focus on the quality of deliberation and the recommendations made. Participatory evaluation methods will also be employed.
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Madrid	Feedback from participants will be gathered through surveys and conversations, assessing both the iDEM app and the participatory process itself.
Barcelona	Evaluation will focus on three main indicators: the existence of a consensus document, the quality of deliberation (e.g. including moderation, control of dominant voices, counting of number of interactions between participants), and feedback from participants, collected through surveys.
Comparison	All pilots aim to use a combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators to evaluate the success of the process, with an emphasis on participant feedback.

4.5. Summary of key findings of section four

All pilots will pre-train both facilitators and participants on how to use the app. Whether moderators will be trained has not been decided. All pilots include training for both participants and facilitators in using the iDEM app. This ensures that everyone involved can effectively engage with the technology. The Barcelona case will train participants shortly before the first session of the process.

While all pilots involve multiple sessions, the frequency and duration differ, with Bologna focusing on preparatory events, Madrid on extended working phases, and Barcelona opting for shorter, more frequent sessions.

All pilots aim to produce recommendation reports, which will encapsulate the insights and conclusions from the deliberative processes. However, as argued in the general advice, all pilots shall be more precise about their capacity to produce a specific output which will then serve as an adequate input at the stage of the addressed policy cycle, in which the topic is situated.

All pilots ensure the relevance of topics to participants' daily lives, though the selection process varies— Bologna (bottom-up process) emphasizes participant-driven issues, while Madrid (top-down process) prefers a topic tied to the community's needs but not related to the participants' social backgrounds. Barcelona (transversal process) prefers topics allowing for group discussions and plenary sessions, as well as lively discussion dynamics.

All three pilots rely on partnerships with local organizations and civil society to ensure effective recruitment and communication. However, Madrid and Barcelona put a stronger emphasis on structured collaboration with specific associations such as Las Rozas Innova for the case of Madrid and NGOs, academic institutions and support persons for the case of Barcelona. Bologna puts an additional focus on social media and digital spaces for recruiting participants.

All pilots deal with the challenge of group size, seeking to balance inclusivity with effectiveness. Bologna and Barcelona opt for smaller groups, while Madrid is exploring how to manage larger participation effectively.

Each pilot plans to use the iDEM service to facilitate participation, though all three face challenges in understanding its full potential and functionalities and in figuring out the most promising scenarios for its usage. All three pilots articulate the desire for a more detailed planning of the UX testing and the preparation of pre-trainings. Bologna intends to use the app during the information phase and it explores possibilities to link the iDEM app to Wordpress or a digital participation platform. Madrid will use the iDEM app in offline situations of deliberation but potentially also in the context of a digital participation platform employed to enable further deliberation between in-person events. The Madrid case is still not entirely aware of the potential use cases of the app and expects further clarification through UX-testing in the following year. The Barcelona case intends to use the iDEM app at each stage of the process.

All pilots recognize the need to avoid participants' fatigue and to incentivize participation. Bologna and Madrid rely on incentives (financial or otherwise), while all three pilots ensure proper pacing and alternation between activities to maintain motivation, considering affective, somatic, cognitive and communicative differences of participants and their needs.

All pilots employ moderators and facilitators to maintain a constructive and trusting environment. Emphasis is placed on enforcing participation rules and the clear definition of roles as well as avoiding dominant voices.

All pilots emphasize the importance of making expert information accessible. Experts are briefed or guided on how to present complex data in simpler terms to ensure inclusivity. Madrid will motivate experts to make use of the iDEM app to simplify their inputs.

All pilots aim to ensure that the outcomes are communicated to relevant policy-makers through direct engagement events or congresses. For the case of Madrid, members of Las Rozas Innova will be present to ensure direct feedback of the participants' inputs to policy-making. The Barcelona case will organize congresses and meetings to create an opportunity for policy-makers and participants to discuss possible outcomes of these inputs in decision-making. The Bologna case will produce different reports for different target audiences of the results, including policy-makers.

All pilots recognize the importance of tailoring their communication strategies to different audiences, including policy-makers, participants, and different issue publics.

All pilots aim to use a combination of qualitative and quantitative indicators to evaluate the success of the process, with a special emphasis on direct feedback from participants.

All pilots plan to keep participants updated, though the specific mechanisms are less defined in the Madrid case and more concretely defined for the case of Barcelona (meetings, DMs, social media) and Bologna (meetings).

A systematic implementation of the recommendations of D4.1. can be expected to take place in the upcoming year when the design phase of the pilots is planned to start. For now, it is still too early to suggest concrete tools, methods and recommendations as the design choices of each pilot are not detailed enough to allow adaptations and interventions in e.g. a moderation plan or a sufficiently reliable GANTT chart of one of the pilots.

5. Concluding remarks

This deliverable presents an overview on the process of transdisciplinary co-production of knowledge which led to these guidelines. It sums up the status quo of design choices for each pilot and provides general advice and recommendations from D4.1 to enhance the inclusivity. By presenting this “snapshot” on design activities and framing them within a theoretically informed perspective on implementing a participatory process which meets quality standards, this deliverable is a substantial contribution to guiding and advancing the pilots’ design activities. As a snapshot also implies, these guidelines are not meant as an exhaustive and once and for all finalized document. It is expected that they will be further developed in accordance with and in response to the ongoing progress in design, testing and piloting activities in the upcoming year.

These concluding remarks center around the future challenges to be taken into account during the design phase to ensure the implementation of a participatory process. These include meeting standards of good quality *and* allowing for participative technology development, through the choice of issues and their alignment with policy cycles, the continuation of participation and deliberation on digital platforms: the testing of the iDEM app and its aims and the documentation of the process with its implications for evaluation and data protection.

First, as we saw none of the processes has yet made a final decision on the topic of the process. It may seem that the choice of a topic is not a pressing issue at the moment, however, it is interrelated with decisions about the recruitment method, the choice of a format and the expected outcome of the process in policy-making. All pilots have more concrete ideas about the formats they will use. They are also about to figure out their recruitment methods.

The next steps to finalize the core set of design choices is to choose a concrete topic, and subsequently, to define the input the process may be able to produce (report, statement, videos, etc), its position in the policy-cycle and its expected impact on policy-making (outcome). This will help identify relevant stakeholders, address publics and policy-makers and sharpen the profile of each participatory process in public communication and in communication with potential participants.

Another choice to be made concerns the usage of digital platforms. While the DoA prescribed for the cases of Bologna and Madrid to test the application on a “web platform”, it is still not clear which platform this will be and which role it will play in the process. In any case, design activities going on at the moment should aim at reducing this uncertainty in order to develop and implement a proper UX-testing strategy for the app.

Concerning the testing of the app, the following issues are still pending for each case (at least in broader terms), which sequence of consecutive events (representing one or more specific format(s)) is planned, which concrete working sessions will be realized at each event, according to which methods and with the help of which tools this will be done. Answering these open questions will allow developing a UX-testing strategy tailored to the needs of each pilot. Nexus could deduce the specific user stories from broader descriptions of the subsequent working sessions (formats, methods and tools, including iDEM). Based on that, they could create testing frameworks and provide advice. For the moment, it is clear that accessibility tests following standardized protocols will be made. Further testing activities are necessary to grasp the capabilities of the app, e.g. in simulated situations of a participatory process or at training sessions with future participants. As already mentioned, the aim and strategy for these testing activities could be better specified as soon as more detailed information on the specific combination of formats, methods and tools for each case are available.

As indicated above, the evaluation of the process and its outcomes entails the proper documentation of the process serving the needs of researchers to create good conditions for acquiring both data and principles of data protection and security. The more intrusive the data gathering methods are (biofeedback, video, image, audio, notes, memories, etc), the higher is the risk related to a damage for the fundamental rights of the data subjects (data protection) or misuses of their data (data security). In particular, the principle of data minimization is key and it implies that researchers critically question the relation between the means of data gathering and the expected outcomes. It therefore may lead to choosing less intrusive means of data gathering, if data of similar or better quality can be gathered with less intrusive means.

The iDEM project will be evaluated by external evaluators and as such, these guidelines can only make very general remarks. In any case, if the evaluation focuses on both impact and process evaluation, it should be clear that impact can only be evaluated if expected outcomes are defined previously. This implies that organizers are well aware of the kind of input their process can produce for a specific stage of a policy-cycle. Secondly, if the evaluation focuses on the process, organizers shall be well aware about the formats, methods and tools they will employ, as the evaluation will focus on the quality of their implementation, their interplay and most substantially, the experiences of the participants.

6. Literature

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Annex 1: Survey questionnaire

Active involvement

Are you/Will you be actively involved in implementing one or more pilots?

1. Questions preparing for the stage „Before the participative process“

1.1 Topic

- Which topics would be relevant for/would you like to address in your participatory process?

1.2 Time

- How long do you expect the participatory event to last? Do you plan a singular event and if so, how long is it supposed to last? Or do you plan a series of 2 (or 3, or 4, etc) events?

1.3 Number of participating citizens

- With how many participants are you planning to implement the pilot?
- What would be the supposed group size of smaller discussion groups?

1.4 Composition of the group of participants

- Do you already have an idea of the intended final composition of the group of participants?
- Do you wish to implement the pilot fulfilling a certain quota of participants from vulnerable groups, e.g. people with cognitive disabilities (and/or elderly, migrants)? If so, how do you define the quota?
- Do you plan to include participants which do not belong to the aforementioned vulnerable groups? If so, what shall be their proportion?

1.5 Recruiting

- How do you plan to recruit the participants (Open call, sortition, through associations, etc...)? Do you plan to gather the relevant socio-demographic characteristics of potential participants?
- How would you proceed and which kind of support do you need?

1.6 Invitation

- How will you invite participants, also keeping in mind the needs of the target groups, e.g. for simple language (e.g. via facilitators, support people, mail, messengers like Whatsapp, phone, etc)?

1.7 Agenda-Setting

- How do you plan to determine the agenda of your process? Do you plan to include experts, stakeholder organizations, political representatives, administration and/or members of the target group in the agenda-setting?
- If so, and which kind of support do you need?

1.8 Targeted inclusion of target groups in the process design

- Do you intend to include and consult future participants at design stage of the process (e.g. by organizing workshops to gather direct feedback on the planned schedule or even more exploratively, to co-produce (parts of) the schedule with future participants)?
- If so, which kind of support do you need?

1.9 Usage of already existing participatory formats

- Is there already a participatory format you would like to use, adapt or develop?
- If so, which kind of support do you need?

1.10 Awareness

- Should an awareness concept be in place and an awareness person/team be present during the participatory process? If so, what should be its function?

1.11 Place and accessibility

- Did you already decide for a (or several) venues where the process will be held?
- Is that place accessible, esp. regarding the needs of cognitively disabled and elderly people?

1.12 Ethical considerations

- Which ethical considerations should be taken into account at an early stage?
- Can you think of any situation during the process in which vulnerable target groups are in need of specific protective measures, e.g. to protect their right to privacy (e.g. the sharing of health data) or other rights?

1.13 Compensation

- Do you plan to compensate participants for their attendance?
- If so, which kind of support do you need?

2. Questions preparing for the stage „During a participative process“

2.1 Design of discussion formats

- Given the specific needs and requirements of the target groups (e.g. difficulties in comprehending oral and written language, need to simplify complex language, experiences of discouragement in political debates, non-native speakers, etc), do you plan to engage the participants in small group discussions and if so, how?
- If you plan to let participants discuss a topic in small groups, how long shall these group discussion sessions last?

2.2 Decision for the type of moderation

- Who is supposed to moderate discussions (e.g. small group discussions, plenum sessions, exchanges between experts and participants, etc)?
- Are you planning to make use of professional moderators who have prior experiences in moderating political discussions with the target groups? Shall moderators receive a specific training beforehand and which aspects should this training cover? Who shall train moderators?
- Which kind of support do you need regarding these points?

2.3 Information and Expert Input

- How will participants be informed on the issue to be discussed?
- Do you plan to invite experts and let them present information about the issue at stake? If so, how shall the experts present the information? Which kind of support do you need?
- Do you plan discussions or Q&A-sessions between participants and experts? If so, which kind of support do you need?

2.4 Digital Tools

- Do you want to use specific digital tools to support your process, for instance, support the interaction among participants (e.g. Projectors, Tablets, ...)?
- If so, which kind of support do you need?
- Do you plan to link the process to a digital participation platform (such as Decidim or others), e.g. for letting participants comment on proposals before discussing them?

2.5 iDEM Service

- How and when do you intend to use the iDEM services during the process? Before, during or after the event?
- Do you have any specific step of the participatory process in mind which the iDEM service would be of particular use?
- Do you need any support to determine situations in which the iDEM service could be a useful assistive tool?

3. Questions preparing for the stage „After a participative process“

3.1 Expected Outcome

- What would be the expected outcome of your process (e.g. recommendations, reports, ideas, voting, videos, etc)?
- How do you intend to communicate the results in a way that it remains understandable by various target groups?

3.2 Relation to political decision making

- Shall the outcomes of the participatory process be considered by political institutions (e.g. local parliaments, administration, regional or national parliament, policy-makers)?

4. Open questions

4.1 Knowledge resources

- What kind of knowledge resources (information, specific exchange, training, inspiration, best/worst practices, etc) do you need to design and implement the pilot(s) you are engaged with?

4.2 Prior Training

- Which kind of training do you or members of your organization need to be sufficiently enabled in implementing the pilot?

4.3 Open remarks

- Do you have any other points which you would like to raise?

Annex 2: Agenda for the participatory design Workshop in Barcelona, October 2024

Innovative and Inclusive Democratic Spaces for Deliberation and Participation

WP4 Technical meeting and Workshop Meeting

Grant agreement	101132431
Project acronym	iDEM
Project start date - duration	01/01/24 - 36 months
Project Coordinator	UPF
WP4 Leader	NEXUS
Dates	16/10/24 - 17/10/24
Schedule	9:00 am - 18:00 - 16/10/24 9:00 am - 16:00 - 17/10/24
Place	Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Barcelona)
Rooms	54.0C09/54.0C10 Edifici Tallers (signs will be on display) - Link bellow

**Funded by
the European Union**

Attendees	
Horacio Saggion	UPF
Sandra Szasz	UPF
Stefan Bott	UPF
Akio Hayakawa	UPF
Josep Lluís Martí	UPF
Cristina Astier Murillo	UPF
Verena Riegler	CAPITO
Thomas Blanchet	NEXUS
Volkan Sayman	NEXUS
Almudena Rascón Alcaina	PIM
John O'Flaherty	MAC
Eleonora Severa	ANFFAS
Octavio Barriuso Varela	CIB
Claudia Mazzanti	AAIT
Rainer Maria Baratti	AAIT
Laura Trujillo Parra	IMPD
Alba Mestres	IMPD
Sergi Morera	IMPD
Eva Garcia Chueca	BOO
Carlo Eugeni	UOL
Nouran Khallaf	UOL
Serge Sharoff	UOL

How to get there

Campus Poble Nou: <https://www.upf.edu/es/web/campus/campus-poblenou>

we are in the same campus, different building, following is a map of the Poble Nou Campus, for you to follow, last time we were in bullet "51"

This time we are in Tallers 54.0C09/54.0C10

Signs will be on display

Tallers area

Roc Boronat, 138
08018 Barcelona

Tel.: (+34) 93 542 20 00
Fax: (+34) 93 542 20 02

- **Metro:** Line 1 Glòries
- **Tram:** T4 Glòries (Ca l'Aranyó) - T5 i T6 Glòries (La Farinera)
- **Bus:** H14, 7, 92
- **How to get here:** [BarcelonaGuia](#) | [Google Maps](#)

⌚ Weekdays: from 8 am to 10 pm (from 8 am to 9 pm, at the Library/CRAI). In exam periods, open Saturdays and holidays. And extended until 1 am, at the Library/CRAI.

WIFI UPF HOW TO CONNECT

Description

Instructions for connecting to it

operation

Resolution of incidents

ask us

Follow these steps:

1. Turn on Wi-Fi on your device.
2. Connect to the **guest@upf** network .
3. A portal automatically opens.

If you haven't registered before or if your registration has expired:
(see [Operating characteristics](#))

1. Press the option **Don't have an account?**
2. Enter your phone number **(*)** , read and accept the terms of use and the privacy policy and click on **Register** . On the phone you indicated, you will receive an SMS message from the **UPF guest** sender with a 3-digit numeric code.
3. Reconnect to **guest@upf.edu** and enter your phone number and the code you received.
4. Accept the usage policy and press **Continue** .
5. You are now connected and can open your applications or browsers with an Internet connection.

If you had already registered:

1. Enter your phone number **(*)** and the code you received when registering. If you received more than one code, enter the newest one.
2. Press continue.
3. You are now connected and can open your applications or browsers with an Internet connection.

(*) If you have an international number, indicate first the "+" symbol followed by the prefix of your country followed by the mobile number. For example **+54123456789**

Hotels around the area

The express holiday inn, basic and clean 3 streets away

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/uSg8bpd8ysqe6N9F9>

Address: C. de Pallars, 203, Sant Martí, 08005 Barcelona

Ibis is good with more facilities, 3 streets away

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/Gw6WW5DLqaLCVl9l6>

22 · C/ de la Ciutat de Granada, 99, HB004372, Sant Martí, 08018 Barcelona, Spain

Travelodge, 6 blocks away but still quite close

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/wpByY2KANTq1unQb9>

C/ de Lull, 170, Sant Martí, 08005 Barcelona, Spain

The four points, Sheraton is close by as well, 2 streets away, more pricey

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/bU3plieVh7mFj9EH8>

Av. Diagonal, 161, 163, Sant Martí, 08018 Barcelona, Spain

If you check Poblenou, Sant Marti (our neighbourhood you will find many more, good luck!)

Schedule

Prior to the workshop:

Nexus will prepare a survey to assess the needs and requirements of the partners focusing, among others, on:

- **Goal of the process/expected outcome**
- **Topic**
- **Location**
- **Expected Target groups**
- **Timing**
- **Moderation**
- **Specific techniques/formats to be implemented**
- **When/how the technology has to be implemented**

16/10/24 - 9:00 - 18:00

09:00-10:30: Input and contextualisation of the workshop

- Presentation and aim of the workshop and the agenda (nexus)

- Update on participatory processes (what is good participation, update on D.4.1. With formats, techniques etc...) (nexus)
- Question/Discussion

10:30-11:00 - Coffee Break offered by UPF

11:00 - 12:15 or 12.30: Needs and requirements before deliberation

- **Group work: We split up into three groups (~ 6 people per group, groups are sorted by engagement in pilots for those who are actively engaged & interest for all others)**
- Each group receives the following materials (5 min):
 - A short A4 handout summing up the tasks of this group phase
 - Handout presenting the survey results (only results concerning the phase before deliberation)
 - 6-3-5 Brainwriting - template
 - Template for drawing/writing a roadmap
- Introduction to group work (5 min)
- Group work with three sessions (65 min in total):
 - Individual reading of the survey results (5min)
 - Brainwriting 6-3-5 (40min)
 - Drawing a roadmap for the phase before deliberation: milestones and challenges (20 min)
- Presentation of the results of each group and discussion (15 min)

12:30-13:00 : Update on technical side (NLP) and AI (?)

13:00 - 14:00 Lunch offered by UPF

14:00 - 15:30: Needs and requirements during deliberation

- **Group work: We split up into two groups as the tech-related project members will split up now (~ 6 people per group, groups are sorted by engagement in pilots)**
- 1. Each group receives the following materials (5 min):
 - A short A4 handout summing up the tasks of this group phase
 - Handout presenting the survey results (only results concerning the phase during deliberation)
 - 6-3-5 Brainwriting - template
 - Template for drawing/writing a roadmap
- 2. Introduction to group work (5 min)
- 3. Group work with three sessions (65 min in total):
 - a. Individual reading of the survey results (5min)
 - b. Brainwriting 6-3-5 (40min)

- c. Drawing a roadmap for the phase during deliberation: milestones and challenges (20 min)
4. Presentation of the results of each group and questions (15 min)

15:30- 16:00 Coffee Break offered by UPF

16:00 - 17:30: Needs and requirements after deliberation

- Each group receives the following materials (5 min):
 - A short A4 handout summing up the tasks of this group phase
 - Handout presenting the survey results (only results concerning the phase after deliberation)
 - 6-3-5 Brainwriting - template
 - Template for drawing/writing a roadmap
- Introduction to group work (5 min)
- Group work with three sessions (65 min in total):
 - Individual reading of the survey results (5min)
 - Brainwriting 6-3-5 (40min)
 - Drawing a roadmap for the phase after deliberation: milestones and challenges (20 min)
- Presentation of the results of each group and discussion (15 min)

17:30 End of Day 1

17/10/2024 - 9:00-16:00

09:00 - 10:00 - Finalisation of the processes/Roadmaps (if needed) (for all); alternatively: Construction of a GANTT-Chart for each pilot

1. Each pilot forms one group (others join depending on interest/involvement) (5min)
2. Each roadmap will be transformed into a GANTT chart with more precise tasks and a clearer temporal structure (40)
& Support needs for each step/milestone can be added, if there is still enough time
3. Presentation of GANTT-charts, each group has 5min (15min)

10:00 - 11:00 Give-and-Take-Matrix

A digital document will be shared with a give-and-take -matrix

1. Each partner should fill in his or her column/row indicating what the partner is expecting to give to and what to take from other partners, bearing in mind the results of the discussions of day one and two (30min)
2. Each partner present his/her points to the plenum + questions (30min)

11:00 - 11:30 Coffee Break offered by UPF

11:30 - 12:30 - Conclusion and next steps (evaluation, remaining challenges and capacity building (when, how?))

1. Short summary of group works (nexus) (15min)
2. Joint discussion on the following points (nexus documents the discussion in a digital document):
 - a. Evaluation - How shall each pilot integrate external evaluators?
 - b. Capacity Building - How exactly do you imagine capacity building? Which activities of capacity building can be realised for all pilots? Which capacity building activities are only needed for a specific project partner or some partners? Do we need external expertise for some formats?
 - c. Remaining challenges: Which challenges were not addressed or not sufficiently addressed?

12:30 - 14:00 Lunch offered by UPF

14-15:30 group exercise for text selection (focus on possible sources), by CAPITO

15:30 - 16:00 Wrap-up and closing

1. Gather feedback on the workshop
2. Outlook on upcoming activity

16:00 End

6 blocks:

Day 1:

1. Block Inputs: What is AI? What is NLP? What is good participation? (+models)
2. Needs & requirements: before deliberation
 - a. Development of roadmaps
3. Needs & requirements: during deliberation
 - a. Continued roadmap
4. Needs requirements: after deliberation
 - a. Completion roadmap

Day 2:

5. Processing of the results
 - a. Typical trade-offs of organized participation
 - b. Drawing/documentation
6. Conclusion/next steps (findings from practice ((time, organizational; ...); evaluation; schedule/GANTT per pilot; how do you imagine capacity building?))

Survey:

We ask the organizers: What do the organizers of the pilots need to have?

Parallel Technical Session: Day 1 14:00-17:00

14:00-14:30 Data Collection Strategy (Verena)

14:30-15:15 Text Complexity Prediction (Nouran)

15:30-16:15 Complex Word Identification (Stefan)

16:30-17:00 iDEM Infrastructure (John)

Day 2 11:00-17:00

11:00-11:30 Text Simplification with LLMs and Prompting (Akio)

11:30-12:00 Decidim + iDEM (Sandra)